

LAUDS FACTORIES

D4.3 – Call Documentation (round 2)

19 May 2025

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Summary

This document represents the deliverable D4.3 “Call Documentation (round 2)”, which is framed within the LAUDS Factories project’s WP4 “Open Calls & Implementation” and consists of the LAUDS Replication Open Call. The objective of this WP is to mobilize external SME and creatives into circularity projects focusing on sustainable transition of urban footprint and value creation replicating the solutions presented. To do so, WP4 is responsible for the organization and management of two open calls. The deliverable D4.3 presents the documentation that formalizes the rules and procedures for SME and

creatives participating in the Open Call Replication. First, the document provides a description of the Open Call objectives and timeline planned. Then, the initial documentation is presented.

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1. Objectives of Open Call | LAUDS Replication

The second Open Call, **LAUDS Replication**, aims to expand the reach of the LAUDS factory model by selecting diverse teams to first develop and refine their projects within an existing LAUDS Factory, and then use their experience to establish a new LAUDS Factory in a different location, tailored to local needs and conditions. Through this initiative, collaboration among artists, designers, creatives, architects, and technology providers is fostered, creating an environment where innovation and co-design drive the development of a local manufacturing ecosystem.

One of the primary goals is to replicate the LAUDS factory model while adapting it to the specific needs of the chosen location. Instead of a one-size-fits-all approach, the project encourages participants to integrate the core principles of LAUDS factories into their unique urban and cultural contexts, ensuring that each new hub remains aligned with the overarching vision while responding effectively to local challenges and opportunities.

The project seeks to support a minimum of eight experiments, each designed to collaborate closely with LAUDS Factories at a local level in initiatives that will actively contribute to a more sustainable future, focusing on key areas such as mobility, energy, and agriculture. Driving the adoption of greener solutions, these experiments will promote the integration of technical expertise with artistic vision, fostering innovative approaches that blend creativity with cutting-edge technology. Through this synergy, the project aims to enhance sustainability efforts while encouraging cross-disciplinary collaboration that bridges technical development with artistic expression.

2. Timeline of Open Call | LAUDS Replication

Figure 1 presents the timeline for the LAUDS Replication Open Call, outlining all activities and deadlines established and agreed upon within the consortium. Beyond setting the schedule, the Open Call concept and challenges were carefully designed through close collaboration with all consortium members, with a particular emphasis on input from the LAUDS Factories hosts, ensuring alignment with the project's vision and fostering a shared commitment to its successful implementation.

The Challenges for Open Call were submitted to a Public Voting that opened on the **18th of February** and remained opened until the **4th of March**, this activity aimed to involve the community in identifying the most urgent challenges, ensuring their voices played a key role in shaping the priorities of the call. The Open Call is set to be launched on the **2nd of June 2025**, and it's predicted to close on the **4th of September 2025**, giving approximately 3 months for applicants to submit their applications. A Webinar will be taking place on the **18th of June** that will be made available on the project's website¹, this Webinar will present the LAUDS Factories project main concept, and will count with, at least, one representative of each host institution to present the available challenges

¹ <https://lauds.eu/>

LAUDS Replication Timeline

Figure 1 - OC2 Timeline

3. Evaluation Plan of Open Call | LAUDS Replication

The received applications for the LAUDS Replication Open Call will be evaluated against criteria of technical approach and art-tech congruency, innovation potential and impact, technical capacities and cost-benefit. The selection jury will comprise:

- Members of the consortium, namely the representatives of the LAUDS Factories presenting the challenges to which applications have been presented.
- External experts with relevant experience and knowledge.

Evaluation process includes two steps – remote evaluation and consensus meeting, as presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - Evaluation Process

Within the remote evaluation process, applications will be scored based on the following criteria:

- **EC1. Technical approach & Art-Tech congruency:** Soundness of concept, quality of objectives and innovative elements of the proposal. Interaction with hosting LAUDS factory. Synergy between artists/designers and technology providers will be assessed.
- **EC2. Innovation potential and impact:** Originality and novelty of presented ideas. Economic, environmental and social impact of the proposed contribution.
- **EC3. Technical capacities:** Demonstration of competences and skills of the project team and its capacity to carry out the activities of the proposal. Complementarity of partners.
- **EC4. Cost-benefit:** Adequacy of budget requested against the proposed work plan.

Each criterion will be scored between 0 (Fail) and 5 (Excellent). The final score (including for each criterion) is the average of the scores provided by evaluators. The threshold for each criterion is three (3). This indicates that if a proposal scores less than 3 in any criterion the proposal is automatically rejected. Innovation potential and impact criterion is given a weight of 1.5 to determine the final ranking.

The evaluators will then hold a consensus meeting to prepare a single consensus Evaluation Summary Report (ESR) for each proposal, representing opinions and scores on which the evaluators agree and which they will sign. The decision on the ranking list and on the selected applicants shall be sought by consensus, and whenever not feasible, by majority vote of 2/3. From the consensus meeting two lists will prepare:

- List of the selected projects: identification of the applications selected for funding.
- Reserve list: identification of the applications to be selected for funding, if any of those listed is unable to proceed to the implementation.

4. Documentation of the Open Call | Replication

The LAUDS Replication Open Call is supported by a set of documents that provide essential information to potential applicants, as well as templates that must be submitted as part of the application process. These documents are briefly described below and included as annexes to this report.

Annex 1: Call for Proposals

This annex provides an overview of the LAUDS Factories project and its objectives, which serves as context for applicant's proposals.

Annex 2: Catalogue of Challenges

This annex details each challenge proposed for the Open Call | LAUDS Replication, including the proposed challenges and expected outcomes.

Annex 3: Guideline for Applicants

This annex represents the detailed information, rules, and procedures for participation in the Open Call | LAUDS Replication. It addresses who is eligible to participate, where to submit a proposal and what information must be included, how the evaluation process is carried out, the implementation of awarded sub-projects, and additional responsibilities when participating in the programme.

Annex 4: Application Form

This annex replicates the specific open call proposal form that applicants must complete and which can be found at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/lauds-call-2-replication>.

Annex 5: Technical Annex

This annex is a Word template that indicates all the sections that must be completed as part of the technical proposal to be submitted. The sections are: i) Status of the Project, ii) Project objectives and activities, iii) Project Activities, Outputs and Cooperation, iv) Innovation potential and impact, v) Project Exploitation and Scale-Up, including communication and dissemination measures, vi) Team Competences and Expertise, vii) Additional pages for sketches/reference image (if any). The sections are aligned with the evaluation criteria. This is a mandatory annex to the proposal.

Annex 6: Budget Template

This annex is an Excel file to present a simplified estimation of costs for the implementation of the proposed project that should be provided as part of the application.

Annex 7: Guidelines for Evaluators

This annex includes all the guidelines and instructions for evaluators. Also includes the template for Individual Evaluation Report.

Annex 8: Sub-grant Agreement Template

This annex is a template of the sub-grant agreement (contract) that will be signed by all parties (LAUDS Factories Project Coordinator (as Contractor), the Host Organization and the beneficiary). It describes all the rights and responsibilities of the signing parties.

Annex 9: Declaration of Honour

This annex must be signed by legal entities submitting a proposal, which declare that all conditions of the open call are accepted by the entity's legal representative.

Annex 10: SME Declaration Form

This annex must be signed by SMEs presenting proposals, stating that all the conditions specified by the European Commission in the definition of SME are fulfilled.

Annex 11: Bank Account Information

This annex is an administrative document that collects information about the bank account to which payments to beneficiaries will be made.

Annexes

Annexes

Annex 1: Call for Proposals

This annex provides an overview of the LAUDS Factories project and its objectives, which serves as context for applicant's proposals.

LAUDS Factories

CALL

FOR

PROPOSALS

LAUDS REPLICATION

OC2-2025-laudsrep-01

CALL COORDINATOR:

INOVA+

Co-funded by
the European Union

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1. INTRODUCTION

This is the second Open Call for Experiments Proposals under the project **LAUDS Factories - Local Accessible Urban Digital and Sustainable Factories: New European Bauhaus Approach to Open and Decentralised Urban Manufacturing¹**, which is co-funded by the European Union.

Through the *Open Call #2 | LAUDS Replication (OC#2)*, LAUDS project aims to take its model to other contexts, by supporting hybrid teams (composed of at least artistic/creative entities and technology providers) to collaborate and co-design the development of a LAUDS factory, replicating the models and adjusting them to the contextual specificities, while answering to pressing challenges related to the mobility, energy and agriculture/food production sectors.

Funding per Experiment: EUR 27 000
Number of Experiments to be Funded: 8 Experiments
Experiments expected duration: 6 to 9 months (Nov.2025–Aug.2026)

¹ Project website: <https://lauds.eu/>. Project on Cordis: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101135986/en>

2. BACKGROUND

Societal transformation and appropriate innovation governance models along with new technical solutions are seen as important pillars in solving environmental problems. Today, seeds of this societal and industrial transformation exist.

Digital communities gather around open-source innovative projects, makers create collectives of professionals, artists and tinkerers in third places to **co-create solutions while designing global and manufacturing local**.

SMEs, looking for more sustainable new business models, are inventing circular and sense-making businesses in various territories. An **agile co-creation based on “do no significant harm” principle** is a known development practice that can be expanded to the whole manufacturing chain.

The transition to a low carbon, resource efficient, circular and sustainable bioeconomy, with its technological potentials and proven applications and initiatives like the **New European Bauhaus** offers solutions to the challenges society is facing today.

Transformation processes towards a climate positive society call for finding new ways and patterns of decentralised, local and urban manufacturing within existing ecosystems. Small, versatile factories, close to innovators and customers allow various types of customised products to be produced in regions close to the consumer that create a virtuous cycle based on design-produce-use-repair-recycle loops.

Such factories can enable the production of customised products in small series at a cost comparable to mass-produced products, helping to promote new skills and new job opportunities, and create activity in the local area, with the subsequent economic benefits to the community.

By bringing production inside the local market, small factories can reduce transportation costs and time, increase resilience by cutting the supply chains and making it easier for customers to access the products they need and subsequently reduce the required resources of the production process, which aligns with the sustainability goals of many modern consumers and those envisioned by the EU.

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3. OBJECTIVES AND CHALLENGES

LAUDS Factories — **Local, Accessible, Urban, Digital and Sustainable Factories** — is an innovative concept aiming at promoting and creating small, versatile factories in local and urban areas to co-create and produce customised products in small series.

The project aims to incorporate innovative and active resiliency capabilities at production and supply chain levels, as part of a green, circular, and digital transformation. The project seeks to create an increased personalised experience for customers, enhance their satisfaction and loyalty to local manufacturing businesses and, more generally, to boost local development of open and decentralised manufacturing ecosystems.

The *Open Call #2 | LAUDS Replication* will award 8 Experiments, proposed by hybrid teams, that replicate LAUDS models and adjust them to the contextual specificities, while answering to pressing challenges related to the mobility, energy and agriculture/food production sectors (*see challenges detailed descriptions in the OC#2 - Catalogue of Challenges*).

The selected teams will implement their projects in cooperation with one of the *LAUDS Factories Experiments Hosting Partners* (see *Table 1*), benefiting from the guidance and support of LAUDS Factories partners, while contributing to improve the LAUDS Factories Partners and Project processes and procedures, connecting potential manufacturers partners, creatives and end-users.

Within the proposed activities, Applicants are asked to explore the LAUDS values², implementing activities such as development of open-source hardware either as new solutions or further development of existing solutions; conception of novel uses of technologies that help push for green solutions; or replication of alternative design methods using artistic practices creating new industrial models, following the LAUDS values.

² Local, Accessible, Urban, Digital and Sustainable.

Table 1 - LAUDS Factories Experiments' Hosting Partners and related Challenges

LAUDS Factories Experiments Hosting Partner	Domain	Challenges
 Bauhaus-Universität Weimar (Germany)	Mobility	Designing effective solutions for active and non-motorized transport
	Energy	Reimagining energy delivery systems
METALAB <u>METALAB</u> (Ukraine)	Agriculture/ Food	Advancing Urban Sustainability Through Community-Based Green Education and Cultivation Systems
	Agriculture/ Food	Local production of affordable and sustainable materials for agriculture
SUPSI <u>University of applied sciences and arts of Southern Switzerland.</u> (Switzerland)	Mobility	Imaginative solutions for inclusive and accessible transportation
	Energy	Reusing Fabrics and Advanced Biomaterials for Energy-Efficient Interiors
TMDC <u>Taller para la Materialización y el Desarrollo de (grandes) Conceptos</u> (Spain)	Mobility	Reducing carbon footprint of urban transport systems
	Energy	Democratizing energy through DIY renewable energy solutions
 <u>Université de Lorraine, Lorraine Smart Cities Living Lab</u> (France)	Agriculture/ Food	From Waste to Resource: community-driven food waste valorisation solutions
	Mobility	Innovative solutions for informed, accessible decision-making

Detailed information about the challenges is available in the **OC#2 - Catalogue of Challenges**, accessible on the **OC#2 Call Kit Documentation** at the LAUDS Factories website: <https://lauds.eu/open-calls/2>.

The *Open Call #2 | LAUDS Replication* expects to select two (2) proposals per 3 LAUDS Factories, one (1) challenge per 2 LAUDS Factories and at least one (1) proposal per domain. Nevertheless, the LAUDS Factories Project reserves the right to decide differently on this distribution based on the quality of the proposals received.

4. LAUDS BENEFITS

OC#2 of LAUDS Factories will support at least 8 Experiments with:

- Up to 27.000 EUR each Experiment;
- 3 types of mentoring and assistance: administrative (provided by INOVA+), technical (provided by LAUDS Factories Hosting Partner) and communication (SUPSI). Meetings to be scheduled as needed;
- 1:1 meetings with experts on specific topics identified by selected teams (e.g. IPR, business models);
- Training workshops (collective) offered by the LAUDS Factories Partners and other experts;
- Networking and promotion opportunities.

LAUDS Monitoring & Mentoring

5. EXPECTED OUTPUTS

Selected Experiments shall implement activities addressing the challenges, objectives and requests mentioned in this *Call for Proposals*. Experiments will be asked to deliver at least the following outputs:

- 1) one **challenge-focused report** describing the developed replication process including a blueprint of the proposed solution (where relevant);

- 2) one **final report** on the collaboration with the LAUDS Factories Partners;
- 3) **Photos, videos and social media content** reporting the process, outputs and events implemented within the experiment. At least 10 photos, 2 short videos; 3 key short stories for social media (Instagram and LinkedIn);
- 4) **A visual LAUDS Blueprint Canvas to document and communicate the process. The Blueprint is developed with the support of the communication coaches of SUPSI.**
- 5) **Feedback on Experiment's impact through short surveys and interviews;**
- 6) **Participation in one LAUDS Factories event promoted within the project LAUDS Factories.**

Templates will be provided to selected Experiments.

6. EU FUNDING VISIBILITY AND EXPERIMENTS PROMOTION

Selected Teams must clearly acknowledge the European Union's contribution in all activities related to the selected Experiment and seek to promote as much as possible the Experiment and its activities through communication and dissemination actions. Selected teams will be required to give prominence to the name and emblem of the European Commission on all their activities implemented under the co-financed action. Where appropriate, they should also use the LAUDS Factories logo and visuals. Guidelines will be provided to the successful applicants. Moreover, Applicants will be asked to include in applications **plans to promote their Experiments** through appropriate dissemination and communication actions.

7. TIMETABLE

The indicative schedule for the different stages of the selection procedure is as follows:

Table 2 - LAUDS Replication Open Call Timetable

Stage of the Open Call	Planned Date
Call opening	2 June 2025
Deadline for applications submission	4 September 2025 – 17:00 (CET), Brussels time
Applications' Evaluation	05 September – 30 September 2025
Information on evaluation results	7 October 2025
Sub-grant agreement signature	30 October 2025
Experiment execution timeframe	1 November 2025 – 31 August 2026

The LAUDS Factories project reserves the right to adjust the planned timetable and any change will be announced in the communication channels of the project.

8. AVAILABLE BUDGET

A total budget of 216.000 Euros is allocated to the LAUDS Replication Open Call to fund the participation of at least 8 Experiments³.

Selected Experiments will receive a grant that **cannot surpass 27.000€** per Experiment. The grant will be paid in three lump sums:

- one at the beginning of the project (40% with the sub-grant agreement signature),
- the second with an interim assessment (40%),
- and at the end of the project pending the achievement of agreed milestones and deliverables (20% with expected outcome).

At the proposal stage, applicants must submit a budget overview for the implementation of their Experiment, including the expected costs concerning Staff Costs; Travel Costs; Equipment/Tech Consumables Costs (depreciation) and, whenever required, Subcontracting Costs. Following the standard flat rate applicable in the Horizon Europe programme, a flat rate of 25% for overheads will be applied.

All payments will be subject to tax and other reductions according to the laws of all involved countries.

Multiple applications are possible under this call. In these cases, applicants need to submit one application form per Experiment proposal. However, only one proposal can be awarded per applicant.

9. ADMISSIBILITY AND DOCUMENTS

- Proposals must be submitted **electronically** via <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/lauds-call-2-replication>. Paper or email submissions are NOT admissible.
- Proposals must be submitted in **English** using the Application Form and templates provided on the submission page.
- Proposals must be complete, containing all requested documents and information requested in the Application Form.
- Additional supporting documents (e.g., bank account validation) will be requested only from selected applicants.

Consult all detailed guidelines in LAUDS OC#2 Guide for Applicants.

³ The LAUDS Factories Consortium reserves the right not to award all available funds or to redistribute them between the open calls planned within the project, depending on the quality of the applications received and the results of the evaluation.

10. SELECTION CRITERIA

Applications meeting the eligibility criteria will be evaluated according to four criteria, as presented in the Table next:

Table 2 - LAUDS Replication Open Call evaluation criteria

Evaluation Criteria (EC)	Description
EC1. Technical approach & Art-Tech congruency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soundness of concept, quality of objectives and innovative elements of the proposal. Interaction with hosting LAUDS factories. • Quality and effectiveness of the work plan and outputs. • Synergy between members of the hybrid team will be assessed.
EC2. Innovation potential and impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Originality and novelty of presented ideas. • Relevance and credibility of the expected impacts of the proposed contribution, including at local, economic, environmental and social levels. • Quality of measures for exploitation and scale-up, including communication and dissemination actions.
EC3. Technical capacities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstration of competences and skills of the project team and its capacity to carry out the activities of the proposal. • Complementarity of partners.
EC4. Cost-benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adequacy of budget requested against the proposed workplan.

* Innovation potential and impact criterion is given a weight of 1.5 to determine the final ranking.

Each criterion will be scored from 0 to 5, following the rationale below:

0	Fail	The proposal fails to address the criterion or cannot be judged due to incomplete or missing information.
1	Poor	The criterion is inadequately addressed or there are serious inherent weaknesses.
2	Fair	The proposal broadly addresses the criterion, but there are significant weaknesses.
3	Good	The proposal addresses the criterion well, but several shortcomings are present.
4	Very Good	The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but a small number of shortcomings are present.
5	Excellent	The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.

The threshold for each criterion is three (3). Any proposal receiving a score below 3 in any single criterion will be automatically rejected without further review. Only proposals meeting or exceeding the minimum thresholds will advance to the competitive selection phase. For proposals that successfully pass the threshold requirements, final selections will prioritize those with the highest cumulative scores across all criteria. The final selection will consider the following planned distribution:

- Two (2) proposals per three LAUDS Factories Hosts;
- One (1) challenge per two LAUDS Factories Hosts;

- A minimum of one (1) proposal from each domain.

Nevertheless, the LAUDS Factories Project reserves the right to decide differently on this distribution based on the quality of the proposals received.

11. PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA

The reply to any call for proposals involves the recording and processing of personal data (such as name, e-mail, and address). Such data will be processed pursuant to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016⁴ on the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data. Unless indicated otherwise, the questions and any personal data requested that are required to evaluate the application in accordance with the call for proposal will be processed solely for that purpose by the LAUDS consortium.

12. CONTACT INFORMATION

If, after reading the **Guide for Applicants** and the **FAQs** available in the call webpage, you have further questions regarding the Open Call process, please send us an email at lauds.opencall@inova.business.

The LAUDS consortium will provide information to the applicants via LAUDS Factories website, so that the information (question and answer) will be visible to all participants. No binding information will be provided via any other mean (e.g., telephone or email).

** In case of any technical issues, please include the following information in your message:*

- *your name and your email address;*
- *details of the specific problem (error messages you encountered, bugs descriptions, i.e. if a dropdown list isn't working, etc.);*
- *screenshots of the problem.*

⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02016R0679-20160504>

LAUDS OC#2 CALL:

CALL FOR PROPOSALS

GUIDE FOR APPLICANTS

CATALOGUE OF CHALLENGES

LAUDS FACTORIES CONSORTIUM PARTNERS

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT BERLIN / GRENOBLE INP-UGA / G-SCOP LABORATORY / UNIVERSITE
GRENOBLE ALPES / HSU – HELMUT-SCHMIDT UNIVERSITY / UNIVERSITY OF THE FEDERAL
ARMED FORCES HAMBURG / UNIVERSITÉ DE LORRAINE / ZENTRUM FÜR SOZIALE
INNOVATION GMBH / INOVA+, INNOVATION SERVICES, S.A / MAKER V-10 / STICHTING DYNE.
ORG / BAUHAUS-UNIVERSITÄT WEIMAR / FAB CITY HAMBURG E.V. / HIWW UG / FABLAB
DIGITAL FABRICATION AND OPEN INNOVATION LAB SUPSI / MEKANIKA / METALAB / TMDC

[HTTPS://LAUDS.EU/](https://lauds.eu/)

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Annex 2: Catalogue of challenges

This annex details each challenge proposed for the Open Call | LAUDS Replication, including the proposed challenges and expected outcomes.

LAUDS Factories

CATALOGUE

OF

CHALLENGES

LAUDS REPLICATION

OC2-2025-laudsrep-01

CALL COORDINATOR:

INOVA+

Co-funded by
the European Union

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CHALLENGES PRESENTATION

MOBILITY-RELATED CHALLENGES

Challenge M1: Designing Effective Solutions for Active and Non-Motorized Transport

Description: As urban congestion and environmental challenges continue to rise, active mobility presents a sustainable alternative to motorized transportation. However, existing systems often fail to address key needs like accessibility, safety, and seamless integration into urban infrastructure. We invite innovative solutions that enhance non-motorized transport options—such as walking, cycling, and other eco-friendly alternatives. These solutions should focus on improving infrastructure, services, and overall user experience, while prioritizing accessibility and sustainability. The goal is to make non-motorized transport a practical, attractive, and eco-friendly option for people and goods, helping reduce reliance on motor vehicles and fostering healthier, more livable cities.

LAUDS Factory hosting the challenge: BUW

Challenge M2: Imaginative Solutions for Inclusive and Accessible Transportation

Description: Ensuring equitable access to mobility remains a critical challenge for low-income and underserved populations, particularly individuals with disabilities, who face systemic barriers to employment, healthcare, and social inclusion. This challenge seeks practical, cost-effective mobility solutions that prioritize functionality, durability, and adaptability across varied terrains, without reliance on high-cost technologies or complex electronic systems. Emphasis is placed on the use of locally sourced or repurposed materials, modular design principles, and intuitive user interfaces to enable scalable, context-sensitive interventions. Solutions should respond to real-world constraints, including poor infrastructure, limited maintenance resources, and the need for easy local manufacturing or repair.

LAUDS Factory hosting the challenge: SUPSI

Challenge M3: Reducing Carbon Footprint of Urban Transport Systems

Description: Urban transportation is a major driver of carbon emissions, demanding innovative solutions to achieve sustainable cities. The challenge calls for the development of transformative approaches to

decarbonize urban transport systems. Participants are encouraged to explore diverse strategies, such as integrating electric and hydrogen-powered vehicles, advancing shared mobility models, and designing cutting-edge infrastructure that fosters clean, efficient, and accessible transit. Solutions should prioritize reducing environmental impact while enhancing urban livability, accessibility, and resilience, paving the way for greener, smarter, and more connected cities.

LAUDS Factory hosting the challenge: TMDC

Challenge M4: Innovative solutions for informed, accessible decision-making

Description: As technology reshapes the way we navigate truth and the physical-digital divide, reliable access to information plays a vital role in informed decision-making. The challenge invites participants to develop tangible, human-centric solutions that enable users to monitor, verify, and visualize energy consumption and mobility patterns in real-time, fostering sustainable choices in urban transport. Proposals could include interactive tools, apps, or systems that provide insights into energy-efficient routes, shared transport availability, or vehicle energy usage. Integrating actionable and accessible information into these solutions encourages environmentally conscious decisions while promoting trust and inclusivity. Focusing on practicality and scalability, participants will create prototypes designed to empower sustainable mobility habits, reducing environmental impact while enhancing accessibility and user engagement.

LAUDS Factory hosting the challenge: UL

ENERGY-RELATED CHALLENGES

Challenge E1: Reimagining Energy Delivery Systems

Description: Access to energy can be a challenge in areas dependent on centralized delivery systems, which can be vulnerable to disruptions and inefficiencies. However, with the rapid advancement of technology, there is a growing opportunity to move beyond this reliance and explore the potential of autonomous energy systems. These systems could offer a more decentralized and resilient solution to energy distribution, addressing many of the issues associated with traditional infrastructure. How can we creatively reimagine autonomous systems to seamlessly integrate into our daily lives, ensuring their efficiency and reliability while also considering their broader societal, ethical, and emotional implications? This challenge calls for ideas that not only push the boundaries of technology but also spark deeper reflection on the role of autonomy in society, ensuring that these systems are designed with consideration for the collective well-being and future sustainability.

LAUDS Factory hosting the challenge: BUW

Challenge E2: Democratizing energy through DIY Renewable Energy Solutions

Description: Many communities rely heavily on centralized energy systems, making them vulnerable to disruptions and limiting their ability to achieve energy independence. While portable renewable energy systems offer a way to decentralize energy production, they are often expensive and difficult to access, preventing widespread adoption in local communities. This challenge invites you to design accessible, low-cost DIY renewable energy systems that can be developed and maintained by communities themselves. By leveraging open-source technologies and creative engineering, the goal is to empower communities to generate their own clean energy.

LAUDS Factory hosting the challenge: TMDC

Challenge E3: Reusing Fabrics and Advanced Biomaterials for Energy-Efficient Interiors

Description: Rising energy costs, inefficient insulation, and the prevalence of disposable designs are creating significant challenges in the construction of public and private spaces. At the same time, there are underused resources, often considered waste, such as discarded fabric. This challenge calls for aesthetically pleasing and energy-saving solutions that address interior construction needs while promoting fabric reuse. Proposals shall explore and advance the digital craft by incorporating advanced biomaterials or recycled fibers to solve issues like insulation and noise reduction. Focus on local, custom production, to reduce transportation, foster community involvement, and tackle (emotional) obsolescence—where products lose their appeal or function.

Solutions can be tailored to specific environments or use context. Real-world testing will be critical to measure energy savings, user satisfaction, and overall impact, ensuring that the solutions provide lasting benefits to both users and the environment.

LAUDS Factory hosting the challenge: SUPSI

AGRICULTURE/FOOD PRODUCTION -RELATED CHALLENGES

Challenge A1: From Waste to Resource: community-driven food waste valorisation solutions

Description: Food waste is a significant global issue, often discarded without fully harnessing its potential to generate valuable resources, such as bioenergy, compost, or materials. Many existing solutions fail to integrate effectively within local communities or motivate active participation, leading to limited impact and adoption. This challenge invites you to develop scalable, community-driven systems that transform food waste into useful resources. The solutions could include compact, modular units for composting, bioenergy, or material recovery that can be deployed in urban neighbourhoods and should incorporate educational elements and incentives to engage communities and promote sustainable, circular economy practices.

LAUDS Factory hosting the challenge: UL

Challenge A2: Advancing Urban Sustainability Through Community-Based Green Education and Cultivation Systems

Description: Urbanization has not only disrupted local food systems but also widened the gap between citizens and the skills needed to cultivate and sustain green urban environments. This challenge calls for well-designed, scalable solutions that integrate food production, environmental awareness, and hands-on education into the urban fabric. Whether through modular vertical farming systems, intelligent indoor cultivation setups, or multifunctional growing interfaces, the focus is on enabling communities, schools, and shared urban spaces to actively participate in the greening of cities. Solutions should prioritize accessibility to practical knowledge—ranging from basic cultivation techniques to soil health and natural fertilization—while fostering continuous learning and community engagement to build long-term capacity for sustainable urban transformation.

LAUDS Factory hosting the challenge: METALAB, with support of SUPSI

Challenge A3: Local production of affordable and sustainable materials for agriculture

Description: Urban gardeners or organizations focusing on urban food production often struggle with high production costs, wasteful resource use, and limited access to sustainable materials. How can we support urban gardeners or urban food productions with sustainable and affordable materials and tools? This challenge calls for low-cost and locally produced solutions using for instance recycled fabrics, food production byproducts or secondary raw materials from construction sites to reduce food production's environmental impact. We invite you to design biodegradable pots, nurseries, protective materials for young plants, or other innovative solutions integrating low-energy and digital processes like machine development and molding. Focus on simplicity, community engagement, and scalability to meet users' needs while promoting sustainability, real-world adoption.

LAUDS Factory hosting the challenge: METALAB

LAUDS FACTORIES HOSTS PRESENTATION

BUW

Referring to environment as a concept from artistic practice of the nineteen-fifties that emphasizes the mismatch between life and art, the Media Environments Research Chair (GMU) at Bauhaus University Weimar aims to redesign everyday situations, objects, devices and practices. The Multi-layered mixture of cultures and technologies and further, the production of knowledge all call for a permanent repositioning of artistic practices within society. Through transdisciplinary experimentation with art, technology, biology and nature, we aim to challenge our own self-conceptions in a rapidly changing world.

**Bauhaus-
Universität
Weimar**

Along with creating artwork for exhibitions, GMU works throughout everyday situations; cooperations with the sciences and cultural institutions; the internet; game environments and public spaces. We develop audio visual installations; mise-en-scènes; performance and interventions in urban space. Media Environments co-workers work with a variety of tools and techniques to create wearable technology; smart objects; digital visualizations; electro-mechanical sculptures, experimental games and simulations of utopian city planning. Media Environments encourages students to experiment with technological processes, creative coding, DIY electronics and further with species, organisms, plants and animals. At GMU we investigate new ways to perceive ideas of environment by cultivating connections between art, technology, science and nature in adventurous ways.

Resources and technology available to the Hybrid Teams

DIY BioLab

The DIY Biolab is a working environment equipped with professional laboratory equipment to perform (micro)biological experiments. For example, plants, algae and fungi as well as harmless microbes can be cultivated and researched here. The laboratory has a solid basic equipment (glassware, scales, centrifuges, microwave, heating stirrer, incubator, etc.) as well as a sterile workbench and powerful microscopes.

Figure 1. Image from the DIY Biolab, by Media Environments, University of Weimar]. URL: <https://www.uni-weimar.de/en/art-and-design/chairs/media-environments/laboratories/diy-biolab/>

This enables students to engage in an artistic and scientific study of living organisms, in which they can design the respective environmental conditions themselves and observe the reactions of living organisms. For the experiments, only organisms are used in which a health hazard can be excluded and which, for example, are also approved for work in schools. In recent years, work has been carried out with various plants (e.g. duckweed), fungi (e.g. oyster

mushrooms), single- and multicellular microorganisms (e.g. euglena and nematodes) and the so-called slime-mold Physarum Polycephalum. Some impressions of the organisms are shown in the picture gallery below, information on specific projects can be found under 'Projects'.

The DIY (Do It Yourself) aspect of the Biolab refers to the establishment and development of technical processes (DIY microscopes, Arduino Boards, etc.) and interfaces between different systems, whether biological or otherwise. For example, bio-electronics courses are offered which are dedicated to the combination of technology and biology.

Maker's Corner

The Maker's Corner is a dedicated workspace equipped with professional tools to support the DIY Biolab and digital fabrication processes. It features a CNC milling machine and a laser cutter, providing essential resources for precision manufacturing. Our partner facilities at the Interface Design Chair offer an extended range of fabrication tools, including multiple 3D printers, an additional Epilog Laser Fusion M2 laser cutter, and various CNC machines such as Roland CNCs and Shaper Origin, along with other equipment for both digital and analog fabrication. Additionally, Bauhaus University provides access to a diverse selection of workshops and specialized labs, including woodworking, metalworking, electronics, and sound studios. The university also hosts event spaces for conferences, exhibitions, and symposiums, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and knowledge exchange.

Period for cooperation

Experiments may be implemented between October 2025 and March 2026. Co-workers at GMU are available to cooperate directly with the hybrid team from October 2025 to September 2026.

METALAB

At METALAB, we are dedicated to promoting sustainability, community development, affordable housing, and innovative product design. Our projects unite individuals who share a commitment to these values, creating collaborative environments that support collective progress. Our mission is to empower these communities, helping them build inclusive, sustainable, and comfortable living spaces. Currently, we are focused on two impactful projects: POLE and CO-HATY.

METALAB

POLE is a centre for innovation and sustainable development, where traditional crafts meet modern technologies. At METALAB, we envision a collaborative ecosystem that brings together makers from diverse backgrounds. To achieve this, we created a makerspace—a platform for learning, experimentation, and knowledge sharing about production. Central to this initiative are the principles of the circular economy and universal design, ensuring that the space is both innovative and inclusive.

Figure 2. Image from the POLE project, METALAB. URL: <https://metalab.space/en/project/pole/>

and universal design, ensuring that the space is both innovative and inclusive.

CO-HATY emerged in March 2022 as a response to the devastation caused by Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine. In collaboration with the Urban Curators, METALAB has been working to provide housing solutions for those who lost their homes due to the war. Through the efforts of dedicated partners and volunteers, we are renovating buildings, designing spaces with thoughtfulness and care, and furnishing homes with dignity and love.

Resources and technology available to the Hybrid Teams

At POLE, Hybrid Teams are provided with a wealth of resources and advanced technologies to foster innovation and creativity. The makerspace is fully equipped with state-of-the-art facilities to support a wide range of activities.

The Woodworking Studio features professional-grade tools for cutting, milling, sanding, and assembling wooden structures. The Metalworking Studio includes comprehensive equipment for welding, cutting, and shaping metal components. The Ceramics and Molding Studio offers facilities for clay modelling, mold-making, and prototype creation using diverse materials.

Additionally, there are Laser Cutting and CNC Machines, which are high-precision machines used for rapid

Figure 3. Image from the POLE project, METALAB. URL: <https://metalab.space/en/project/pole/>

prototyping and customized production. The 3D Printing and Prototyping Zone includes various 3D printers, enabling the design and testing of intricate components.

The Community and Knowledge Hub provides access to Expert Mentorship and Peer Support, where teams can tap into a network of professionals from various industries who offer guidance on technical challenges and innovation processes. There is also a strong Focus on Circular Design, with an emphasis on integrating circular economy principles to inspire teams to create products with minimal environmental impact and sustainable lifecycles.

In terms of activities and support, POLE offers rapid prototyping and testing, hands-on experimentation with new materials and technologies, small-scale production runs, and collaborative workshops with industry experts and mentors.

Main expectations for the Hybrid Teams

Since the Hybrid Teams will be working on challenges focused on sustainable urban food production, reducing environmental impact, and designing affordable solutions for urban gardeners, our expectations are aligned with creating practical, scalable, and community-driven innovations.

- **Development of Low-Cost, Locally Sourced Solutions**

We expect teams to design cost-effective and easily replicable solutions that make use of recycled materials, food production byproducts, and secondary raw materials from construction sites. The goal is to minimize costs while promoting sustainable practices that can be adopted by urban gardeners and small-scale producers.

- **Integration of Circular Economy Principles**

A key priority is for teams to integrate circular economy principles into their designs. This includes creating biodegradable pots, protective materials, and other cultivation tools that can be produced sustainably and either reused, recycled, or composted at the end of their lifecycle.

- **Simplicity and Real-World Adoption**

We expect teams to focus on simplicity and practicality—solutions should be intuitive and easy to implement for urban gardeners and community organizations. Teams should consider user-friendly designs that require minimal technical knowledge and can be maintained with limited resources.

- **Scalability and Replicability**

We encourage teams to consider scalability from the outset. Solutions should be designed in a way that they can be easily replicated or adapted to different contexts, allowing for broader adoption across various urban environments.

We are excited to see how Hybrid Teams will apply these principles and leverage the METALAB resources to develop impactful solutions that contribute to sustainable urban food production.

Period for cooperation

Experiments may be implemented between November 2025 and August 2026.

TMDC (TALLER PARA LA MATERIALIZACIÓN Y EL DESARROLLO DE CONCEPTOS)

TMDC (Taller para la Materialización y Desarrollo de Conceptos) is a pioneering industrial coworking space located in Barcelona, encompassing 7,000 m² of facilities designed to empower local manufacturing and foster collaboration among artisans, designers, and small businesses. Our mission is to create a vibrant ecosystem that champions sustainability, innovation, and the dignification of work in the manufacturing sector. With access to advanced machinery, training programs, and a supportive community, TMDC facilitates the growth of creative projects and promotes economic resilience within the city.

TMDC

Figure 4. Overview of the A08 assembly area at TMDC, showcasing a spacious and well-equipped workshop where creativity and hands-on projects come to life, TMDC. URL: <https://www.tmdc.es/>

In line with the objectives of the LAUDS project, we are committed to contributing to the establishment of local urban factories that emphasize open and sustainable production practices. By collaborating with a network of partners, we aim to drive innovative solutions that address the unique challenges of urban manufacturing in Europe. Our facility not only serves as a space for fabrication but also as a hub for knowledge exchange and community engagement, fostering a holistic approach to sustainable development.

Resources and technology available to the Hybrid Teams

TMDC is a fully equipped workshop with a diverse array of tools for working with wood, metal, plastic, and electronics. Hybrid Teams have the freedom to use the tools and the space to meet their specific project goals, fostering creativity and innovation in a hands-on environment.

Some of the materials available for use include:

- Wood: Plywood, MDF, hardwoods (oak, walnut, maple), and softwoods (pine, fir).
- Metal: Aluminum sheets, steel rods, copper, and brass.
- Plastics: Acrylic, PETG, polycarbonate, and PVC.
- Electronics: Circuit boards, microcontrollers (e.g., Arduino, Raspberry Pi), and sensors.

All available tools and machinery can be explored here: <https://www.tmdc.es/herramientas-tmdc>.

In addition to the infrastructure, TMDC offers various workshops and induction classes designed to help teams fully understand and maximize the capabilities of our equipment. These workshops cover a wide range of topics, including carpentry, metalworking, CNC milling, and 3D printing. Hybrid Teams are encouraged to participate in any of these courses to enhance their skills and knowledge.

Upcoming courses available for Hybrid Teams include Introduction to Carpentry, Metalworking Fundamentals, CNC Milling Basics and Advanced 3D Printing Techniques.

All courses can be explored here: <https://www.tmdc.es/cursos>

Furthermore, TMDC is home to a thriving community of 170 members with diverse expertise in fields ranging from design and prototyping to engineering and technology. These members, with backgrounds in areas such as robotics, sustainable materials, and electronics, can become invaluable strategic partners for Hybrid Teams seeking to develop and refine their products. Whether you're looking for guidance on industrial design, need assistance with advanced machine settings, or require a partner for collaborative research, the TMDC community is here to support you.

Main expectations for the Hybrid Teams

Hybrid Teams are expected to work in a professional manner within the space. We expect all members of TMDC to take care of the machines and the space. Depending on the skill set from the hybrid team, some inductions are compulsory to be able to use the workshop's machines. Some machines require the induction regardless of the experience of the team members. Besides that, we hope to encounter motivated individuals passionate about their projects.

Period for cooperation

Experiments may be implemented between November 2025 and August 2026.

Figure 5. Image from TMDC. URL: <https://www.tmdc.es/tarifas>

UNIVERSITÉ DE LORRAINE, LORRAINE SMART CITIES LIVING LAB

Led by ERPI laboratory, the Lorraine Smart Cities Living Lab (LSCLL - <https://lf2l.fr/projects/lorraine-smart-cities-living-lab>) is a collaborative project of the Université de Lorraine (UL) to support the early design stage of development of systemic innovations towards an industry 5.0 and sustainable territories. It advocates for a commons-based technology framework and a circular economy, promoting collective resource management for sustainability.

The core competencies are based on structuring collaborative approaches to co-create intermediate design objects (IDO) linking the multilevel perspective of the innovation from technological development, organisation maturity, and the territorial development perspective. At each level, the integration of different stakeholders (e.g. company, providers, partners, academics... and the end-users and/or consumers) along the design and production process is fostered to better understand the socio-technical systems.

Furthermore, UL LAUDS Factory (LSCLL-UL) aims to implement the Do-It-Together (DIT) concept, an alternative co-creation and open-manufacturing process that enables customized production, promoting local manufacturing closer to consumers and open-communities who actively contribute to the production (see: <https://www.inedit-project.eu/>).

Finally, the LSCLL creates the conditions for Public-Private-Population Partnerships (PPPPs) that are aware of the environmental challenges and willing to develop solutions to serve the common good. That means we adopt a quintuple helix approach to disseminate innovation and related practices in the service of Research, Development of Innovations, Training, a Citizen Culture, and environment.

Figure 6. Image by Laurent Dupont, Université de Lorraine - ERPI & ENSGSI. URL: <https://inspiration.dqesip.fr/Espaces/Lieu/WuMr6/>

Resources and technology available to the Hybrid Teams

A physical platform¹

As a research and teaching platform, the LSCLL-UL has a wide range of equipment, some aimed at the general public, others highly specialized. Description of the available equipment can be found in the following pages (in French):

<https://fabmanager.lf2l.fr/#!/machines>

Figure 7. Université de Lorraine - ERPI - LF2L

¹ Please note that as regulations evolve, certain areas of the UL platform may be subject to restrictions.

<https://pluginlabs.univ-lorraine.fr/fiche/lorraine-fab-living-lab/>

<https://inspiration.dgesip.fr/Espaces/Lieu/WuMr6/>

On this last webpage, a description of innovation spaces, including laboratories, within the LSCLL-UL is available.

A 2D-3D-4D process: from co-creation to test by use²

Support to the co-creation of concept (2D) and its suitability for its socio-technical and natural environment. Accompany projects for a validation of the prototype (3D) through an evaluation of the user experience in a real or virtual environment (4D) prior to physical production, to limit the number of trials and errors, while minimising wasted resources. Tests could be set up at LSCLL-UL (control environment), in relevant environment (open environment) or at the Foire Expo de Nancy with the Open citizen lab in pedagogical/citizen workshops, etc.

A territorial network

L'Octroi Nancy: creative, cultural and citizen third place of the city of Nancy, which provides access to additional spaces such as offices, a creative community, etc.

DHDA project: a regional and hybrid collective (entrepreneurs, foresters, artists, farmers, researchers, elected representatives, industrialists, financiers and naturalists, citizens...) to make the most of all the trees in our region.

Period for cooperation

Experiments may be implemented between November 2025 and August 2026.

Figure 8. Université de Lorraine - ERPI - LF2L

² idem

DIGITAL FABRICATION AND OPEN INNOVATION LABORATORY OF SUPSI

The FabLab is the Digital Fabrication and Open Innovation Laboratory of SUPSI, the University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland. The lab facilitates the development of project in which digital skills cross various domains including architecture, construction, design, interaction, and creativity. The facility actively engages with students, lecturers, researchers, companies, organizations, and citizens to promote the open innovation model through the utilization of digital technologies.

University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland

SUPSI

The FabLab collaborates with Institute of Design and other units of the Department of environment construction and design at SUPSI on topics that span from robotic fabrication, interactive products, reuse of constructions site materials to regenerate the territory to AI powered design.

It is the main facility for prototyping and production of MA in Interaction Design SUPSI, the international program dedicated to design and technology located in Mendrisio: www.maind.supsi.ch

Figure 9. SUPSI_FabLab_DACD_CCBYSA_0: General view of the SUPSI FabLab, under CC BY-SA 4.0 License.

Resources and technology available to the Hybrid Teams

The FabLab SUPSI, spanning 300 square meters, provides cutting-edge training to local and national creative communities on emerging technologies. It showcases how fast prototyping can be simplified and made accessible to designers, artists, and makers who are developing innovative products and experiences. The lab offers access to industrial-grade machines for large-scale production, including CNC machines and industrial 3D printers for architecture, sensors and electronics for interactive prototyping, as well as laser cutters and 3D scanners. Additionally, the lab interacts with other construction spaces on the Mendrisio campus, fostering collaboration across various disciplines. The FabLab is powered by the researchers and designers of the SUPSI Design Institute, whose expertise spans design thinking, electronics, and the advanced implementation of interactive installations. The team provides comprehensive support across all stages of design-driven projects, where aesthetics, functionality, and technology converge. Specializing in

human-computer interaction (HCI), user experience (UX) design, and digital fabrication, the team excels in helping clients bring their concepts to life through digital design and prototyping.

Moreover, the FabLab offers strong support in areas such as scalability and business model development, ensuring that projects are well-prepared for real-world applications. With a focus on data-driven processes, the team can assist in digital documentation and project monitoring, ensuring smooth development and seamless scaling of projects.

Figure 10. SUPSI_FabLab_DACD_CCBYSA_3: CNC Milling at the SUPSI FabLab, under CC BY-SA 4.0 License.

Period for cooperation

Experiments may be implemented between November 2025 and August 2026.

LAUDS OC#2 CALL:

CALL FOR PROPOSALS

GUIDE FOR APPLICANTS

CATALOGUE OF CHALLENGES

LAUDS FACTORIES CONSORTIUM PARTNERS

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT BERLIN / GRENOBLE INP-UGA / G-SCOP LABORATORY / UNIVERSITE
GRENOBLE ALPES / HSU – HELMUT-SCHMIDT UNIVERSITY / UNIVERSITY OF THE FEDERAL
ARMED FORCES HAMBURG / UNIVERSITÉ DE LORRAINE / ZENTRUM FÜR SOZIALE
INNOVATION GMBH / INOVA+, INNOVATION SERVICES, S.A / MAKER V-10 / STICHTING DYNE.
ORG / BAUHAUS-UNIVERSITÄT WEIMAR / FAB CITY HAMBURG E.V. / HIWW UG / FABLAB
DIGITAL FABRICATION AND OPEN INNOVATION LAB SUPSI / MEKANIKA / METALAB / TMDC

Co-funded by
the European Union

Annex 3: Guidelines for Applicants

This annex represents the detailed information, rules, and procedures for participation in the Open Call | LAUDS Replication. It addresses who is eligible to participate, where to submit a proposal and what information must be included, how the evaluation process is carried out, the implementation of awarded sub-projects, and additional responsibilities when participating in the programme.

LAUDS Factories

GUIDELINES

FOR

APPLICANTS

LAUDS REPLICATION

OC2-2025-laudsrep-01

CALL COORDINATOR:

INOVA+

Co-funded by
the European Union

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1. INTRODUCTION

This document complements the **LAUDS OC#2 Call for Proposals** document, providing additional information and guidance for interested individuals and entities to prepare proposals for the *Open Call #2 | LAUDS Replication* of the LAUDS Factories Project.

2. GENERAL INFORMATION

2.1. Terms and definitions

This section describes the relevant terms that are used in the open call documentation. Unless otherwise stated, the definition of a term is the one stated in this section.

Term	Definition
OC#2 or OC#2 LAUDS Replication	Second Open Call for Experiments under the project LAUDS Factories, focused on LAUDS Replication.
LAUDS Factories	Refer to the Project <i>LAUDS Factories - Local Accessible Urban Digital and Sustainable Factories: New European Bauhaus Approach to Open and Decentralised Urban Manufacturing.</i> https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101135986/en
LAUDS Partners or LAUDS Consortium	Group of legal entities that are cumulatively responsible for implementing the LAUDS Factories project as defined in the Grant Agreement number 101135986.
Applicant	Group of entities that intends to submit or has submitted a proposal to the funding program (OC#2).
Beneficiary	Group of entities that has submitted a proposal to the funding program, has been accepted for funding and has signed or is in the process of signing a sub-grant agreement.
External evaluator	An expert who has been invited by LAUDS to assist in the evaluation of the proposal submitted to the funding program. Experts cannot have conflicts of interest and are bounded by their own confidentiality agreement.
LAUDS funding program	Program under which the present open call is run. It is defined by the documents and templates provided by the LAUDS consortium as defined in section 4.1.1. The funding program considers several phases: open call for proposals, evaluation, sub-grant agreement (SGA) preparation and signing, and implementation (for selected beneficiaries).
Proposal phase	Period when applicants can submit proposals to the open call. Each open call has a fixed deadline that is automatically enforced.
Evaluation phase	Period when the consortium evaluates and ranks the applications. At the end of the phase, all proposals are notified of the results of the evaluation.
SGA preparation and signing phase	Period when the selected proposals and the consortium complete the administrative procedures to sign the sub-grant agreement and prepare administrative documents.
Implementation phase	Minimum of 6 months period and Maximum of 9 months period, varying according to the submitted proposal, when the work is performed by the beneficiary. At the

end, the project is subject to a formal evaluation made by an internal evaluation team to assess if the project is meeting its objectives.

2.2. Means of submission

The LAUDS Open Call page (<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/lauds-call-2-replication>) will be the entry point for the submission of all proposals to this open call. Any proposal submitted through other channels will be automatically rejected.

2.3. Language

English is the official language for the LAUDS open calls. Submissions done in any language other than English will not be eligible or evaluated.

Moreover, English is the only official language during the whole implementation of the LAUDS funding program. This means that any requested submission of documentation and deliverables will be done in English to be eligible.

2.4. Documentation formats

Any documentation requested in any of the phases of the open call must be submitted electronically in PDF format without restrictions for printing. Documentation must respect the guidelines provided (e.g. for formatting).

2.5. Data protection

The reply to any call for proposals involves the recording and processing of personal data (such as name, e-mail, and address). Such data will be processed pursuant to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016¹ on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data. Unless indicated otherwise, the questions and any personal data requested that are required to evaluate the application in accordance with the call for proposal will be processed solely for that purpose by the LAUDS consortium.

It should be noted that LAUDS requests the minimum information needed to deliver the evaluation procedures or the implementation of the funding program. The “Annex: Bank account information” and “Annex: Sub-grant Agreement template” are provided for reference and will only be requested if the applicant is selected to the program.

2.6. Origin of the funds

Selected applicants will sign a dedicated sub-grant funding agreement with the LAUDS consortium. The funds attached to the sub-grant agreement come directly from the funds of the European project LAUDS Factories² and therefore remain property of the EU until the payment of the balance, whose management rights have been transferred to the project partners in LAUDS via European Commission GA no. 101135986.

¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02016R0679-20160504>

² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101135986> ; <https://lauds.eu/>

As detailed in “Annex: Sub-grant Agreement template”, this relation between the subgrantees and the European Commission (EC) through the LAUDS Factories Project carries a set of obligations to the subgrantees with the EC. It is the task of the sub-grantees to achieve them and of the LAUDS consortium partners to inform about them.

3. ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

The following eligibility criteria, related to the applicants, funding, and proposals apply.

3.1. Applications’ eligibility

All applicants **must** meet the requirements described in this section to be eligible for the LAUDS OC#2:

1. Submissions will **ONLY** be accepted through the page dedicated to the LAUDS Replication Open Call: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/lauds-call-2-replication>.
2. Fit within the target audience as indicated in *section 3.1.1*.
3. Applicants and Experiment are based in EU Member States or Horizon Europe associated countries as indicated in *section 3.1.2*.
4. The application and all requested documents are provided before the OC#2 submission deadline, respecting the guidelines provided (e.g. for formatting) and only in English language (*see section 4 for more details*). Application is composed of the following:
 - Application Online form (<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/lauds-call-2-replication>);
 - Technical Annex (using template provided: oc2-2025-LAUDSREP-01_TechnicalAnnex);
 - Budget overview for the implementation of the proposal (using template provided: oc2-2025-LAUDSREP-01_Budget_Template).
5. Applicants accept the terms and conditions of the LAUDS OC#2.
6. The proposal is within the scope of LAUDS OC#2 objectives as described in the “Call for Proposals” and addresses one of the challenges presented in the “Catalogue of Challenges”.
7. The duration of the proposed Experiment is limited to a minimum of six (6) months and a maximum of nine (9) months.

The additional eligibility criteria as described in the sub-sections next apply too:

3.1.1. Types of applicants

To be eligible, proposals must be presented by a hybrid team composed of a minimum of **2 (two) legal entities** that are considered eligible under Horizon Europe rules. Hybrid teams shall be composed of at least the following two type of entities:

- **Technology providers of digital and emerging technologies:** for-profit legal entities, including start-ups, SMEs and midcaps. A beneficiary is qualified as an SME as defined in the EU recommendation 2003/361³.
- **Artists⁴/designers/creatives/architects from all artistic fields.**
Note: Preference will be given to artists/designers/creatives/architects who have previously engaged in collaborations/practices with science and technology and digital and emerging technologies.

The following additional conditions apply:

- Each hybrid team applying to the call must include at least one technology provider and one artist /designer/creative/architect. Other entities can be involved in the consortium if relevant to the project.
- The participating organisations should not have been declared bankrupt or have initiated bankruptcy procedures.
- The organisations applying should not have convictions for fraudulent behaviour, other financial irregularities, and unethical or illegal business practices.
- There should not be any conflict of interest with any of the LAUDS partners (beneficiaries), as detailed in Section 3.1.3.

If selected, Applicants will be asked to submit documentation supporting their legal status and financial capacity during the sub-grant agreement signing phase.

Note: Third Parties receiving Financial Support from LAUDS through the open call will not become part of the LAUDS Factories Grant Agreement. The LAUDS Factories Grant Agreement will not need to be amended to include the selected beneficiaries.

3.1.2. Eligible Countries

Only Applicants established in any of the following countries are eligible to participate in the LAUDS Open Call:

- The Member States (MS) of the European Union (EU), including their outermost regions.
- Horizon Europe associated countries: according to the updated list published by the EC⁵.

3.1.3. Conflict of interest

Applications will not be accepted from individuals or entities who are partners (beneficiaries) or linked-third parties in the LAUDS Factories consortium or who are formally linked in any way to the partners/linked-third parties of the LAUDS Factories consortium, and their employees and permanent

³ [EC recommendation for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises \(SMEs\) 2003/361/](#).

⁴ An Artist refers to either an SME, a Slightly Bigger Company or a Mid-Cap registered under NACE Code '9003 Artistic creation' or a self-employed individual (freelancer) who undertakes artistic activities as a profession/job occupation, such as a performer, a designer, a composer, an architect, a writer, etc

⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/list-3rd-country-participation_horizon-auratom_en.pdf

collaborators. Any entity with a previous link to a LAUDS Factories beneficiary (e.g., spin-off), will not be accepted, unless a minimum of 2 years has passed since the termination of the link.

Applicants must not have any current and/or potential conflict of interest with the LAUDS Factories Open Call selection process and during the whole program. Applicants must formally and immediately notify the LAUDS Project Coordinator of any situation constituting or likely to lead to a conflict of interest and take all the necessary steps to rectify this situation.

All cases of conflict of interest will be assessed case by case. Applicants must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective evaluation and implementation of the project is compromised for reasons involving economic interest, political or national affinity, family or emotional ties or any other shared interest ('conflict of interests').

If a conflict of interest is discovered and confirmed at the time of the evaluation process, the proposal will be considered as non-eligible and will not be evaluated.

3.2. Proposal multiple submissions

The LAUDS Replication Open Call is a competitive funding programme. Applicants (group of legal entities) can submit multiple applications. In these cases, applicants need to submit one application form per Experiment proposal. However, only one proposal can be awarded per applicant.

3.3. Financial eligibility

The following financial conditions apply for proposals to be eligible:

- The total requested grant per proposal for LAUDS Replication Experiments **cannot exceed €27.000.**
- The selected Experiments will receive a grant that will cover a maximum of 100% of the budget of the submitted proposals.
- Applicants must submit a budget overview for the implementation of their Experiment, including the expected costs concerning Staff Costs; Travel Costs; Equipment/Tech Consumables Costs (depreciation) and, whenever required, Subcontracting Costs. Following the standard flat rate applicable in the Horizon Europe programme, a flat rate of 25% for overheads will be applied.

For approved projects, the funds will be paid in three lump sums:

- one at the beginning of the project (40% with the sub-grant agreement signature),
- the second with an interim assessment (40%),
- and at the end of the project pending the achievement of agreed milestones and deliverables (20% with expected outcome).

All payments will be subject to tax and other reductions according to the laws of all involved countries.

3.4. Other Conditions

Each applicant must confirm:

- It is not under liquidation or is not an enterprise under difficulty according to the Commission Regulation No 651/2014, art. 2.18.

- The proposed project is based on **original ideas** and, going forward, none of the developments foreseen will be limited by third party rights, or are clearly stated in the proposal description if they are limited (including how they will be handled during the project).
- The project is based on work that has not been developed and offered as a commercial product or solution.
- It is not excluded from the possibility of obtaining EU funding under the provisions of both national and EU law, or by a decision of both national and EU authority.

4. OPEN CALL: SUBMISSION AND SELECTION PROCESS

Proposals submitted to the LAUDS OC#2 are submitted in a single stage and evaluated in two steps, as presented below:

4.1. Proposal preparation and submission

The submission of proposals to the LAUDS Replication Open Call will follow the steps listed in this section.

4.1.1. Open call publication and documentation

The open call is supported by the following documentation, which can be found at LAUDS Factories website: <https://lauds.eu/open-calls/2>

#CALL DOCUMENTS:

- **Call for Proposals**, which provides a full set of information regarding the Open Call, including the scope, objectives, and challenges to be addressed in the LAUDS Replication Open Call.
- **Guidelines for Applicants**, which provides an overview of the rules and procedures to participate in the open call, the evaluation process, and other general provisions.
- **Catalogue of Challenges**, which provides a presentation of the LAUDS Factories and the challenges proposed to be addressed by the hybrid teams.

#APPLICATION DOCUMENTS:

- **Application Form**, an online application form, available at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/lauds-call-2-replication>.
- **Technical annex (template)**, a Word template that indicates all the technical information that should be provided as part of the project proposal. It includes the following sections:
 1. Status of the project
 2. Project concept and objectives
 3. Project activities, outputs and cooperation
 4. Innovation potential and impact
 5. Project exploitation and scale-up, including communication and dissemination measures
 6. Team competences and expertise
 7. Additional pages for sketches / reference images (if any)
- **Budget template (template)**, an Excel file to present a simplified estimation of costs for the implementation of the proposed project that should be provided as part of the project proposal.

#DOCUMENTATION FOR SELECTED APPLICATIONS:

- **Sub-grant agreement template**, which provides a template of the subgrant agreement that the successful applicants will be requested to sign.
- **Applicant Declaration of Honour**, which declares that all conditions of the open call are accepted by the legal representative of the entity/ies.
- **Legal Entity Declaration Form**, which evaluates the status of the legal entities participating in the open call.
- **Bank account information**, which collects information about the bank account to which payments will be made.

Applicants are encouraged to read and download all relevant files before proceeding with the submission.

4.1.2. Proposal preparation

Applicants must consider the following steps when preparing their proposal:

1. For the proposal preparation, applicants are required to apply online and answer all mandatory questions (with no exception) of the application form at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/lauds-call-2-replication>.
2. Applicants that do not accept the terms and conditions and that do not upload to the submission platform the following documents will not be eligible:
 - **Technical annex**
 - **Budget template**
3. Technical Annex and Budget shall be downloaded, completed, and uploaded in PDF format.
4. Applicants must respect the guidelines provided in the application documents (e.g. for formatting).
5. Applicants should submit one Application Form per project proposal. Multiple proposals are allowed but only one project can be awarded per beneficiary.
6. Be specific, clear and concise. Respect the character or page limitations.
7. Project proposals must be submitted by **4 September 2025 at 17:00 (Central European Time)**.
8. Queries about applications can be sent by email to lauds.opencall@inova.business before 2 September 2025. We cannot guarantee that emails will be answered after this date. A FAQ (Frequently Asked Questions) section will be posted on the LAUDS Factories project website and updated regularly.

It is strongly recommended that applicants submit their proposal well before the deadline. The failure to submit a proposal on time, for any reason, including network communications delays or working from multiple browsers or multiple browser windows, is not acceptable as an extenuating circumstance. The time of receipt of the application as recorded by the submission system will be definitive.

4.1.3. Proposal submission

Submissions will be done exclusively at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/lauds-call-2-replication>. Any submission not done via this channel will not be eligible.

A full list of applicants will be prepared containing their basic information for statistical purposes and clarity, which will be also shared with EC for transparency.

The deadline for submission of proposals is 4 September 2025, 17:00 (Central European Time).

Once the proposal is submitted, you will receive a confirmation e-mail. If you do not receive this confirmation e-mail, it means your proposal has NOT been submitted. If you believe this is due to a fault in the submission system, you should immediately file a complaint via lauds.opencall@inova.business, explaining the circumstances and attaching a copy of the proposal (and, if possible, screenshots to show what happened).

Applicants can edit their proposal until the OC#2 closure, as the system allows participants to change their contribution. In case you can not edit your application due a technical constraint, please contact LAUDS team at lauds.opencall@inova.business. No updates will be allowed after the OC#2 closure (4 September 2025, 17:00 CET). We highly recommend to avoid updates in the last 48 hours of the call

submission, as the system might not work properly due to the number of users. LAUDS Team does not take responsibility in case you can not submit your application in due time.

4.2. Proposal evaluation and selection

4.2.1. Step 1: Eligibility verification

An initial eligibility verification will be done to filter out and discard non-eligible proposals. Proposals **must meet ALL the eligibility criteria**, as described in section 3.

Proposals marked as non-eligible (for not meeting one or more of the eligibility criteria) will get a rejection letter with a justification. **No additional feedback on the process will be given.**

4.2.2. Step 2: Individual Evaluation Report

Applications meeting the eligibility criteria will move on to the evaluation phase. The evaluation will be done remotely by senior experts from LAUDS partners organizations and external independent experts.

The proposals will be scored based on the criteria below (Table 3).

Table 1 - LAUDS REPLICATION Open Call evaluation criteria

Evaluation Criteria (EC)	Description
EC1. Technical approach & Art-Tech congruency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soundness of concept, quality of objectives and innovative elements of the proposal. Interaction with hosting LAUDS factories. • Quality and effectiveness of the work plan and outputs. • Synergy between members of the hybrid team will be assessed.
EC2. Innovation potential and impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Originality and novelty of presented ideas. • Relevance and credibility of the expected impacts of the proposed contribution, including at local, economic, environmental and social levels. • Quality of measures for exploitation and scale-up, including communication and dissemination actions.
EC3. Technical capacities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstration of competences and skills of the project team and its capacity to carry out the activities of the proposal. • Complementarity of partners.
EC4. Cost-benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adequacy of budget requested against the proposed workplan.

* Innovation potential and impact criterion is given a weight of 1.5 to determine the final ranking.

Each criterion will be scored from 0 to 5, following the rationale below:

0	Fail	The proposal fails to address the criterion or cannot be judged due to incomplete or missing information.
1	Poor	The criterion is inadequately addressed or there are serious inherent weaknesses.
2	Fair	The proposal broadly addresses the criterion, but there are significant weaknesses.
3	Good	The proposal addresses the criterion well, but several shortcomings are present.

4	Very Good	The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but a small number of shortcomings are present.
5	Excellent	The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.

Each evaluator will record his/her individual assessment of each proposal using an Individual Evaluation Report (IER).

4.2.3. Step 3: Ranking of proposals

At the end of the remote external evaluation process, the final scores will be calculated. The final score of each application (including each criterion) is the average of the scores provided by evaluators.

Each criterion has a threshold, which is three (3). Any proposal receiving a score below 3 in any single criterion will be automatically rejected. Only proposals meeting or exceeding the minimum thresholds will advance in the competitive selection phase.

Proposals that successfully pass the threshold requirements will be ranked based on their overall score (sum of scores for criteria 1 to 4). Applications will be ranked in lists considering the following planned distribution:

- Two (2) proposals per three LAUDS Factories Hosts;
- One (1) challenge per two LAUDS Factories Hosts;
- A minimum of one (1) proposal from each domain.

Nevertheless, the LAUDS Factories Project reserves the right to decide differently on this distribution based on the quality of the proposals received.

In case of a tie, the following rules will apply:

- **Rule 1:** Priority will be given to proposals that have the highest score on **EC1. Technical approach & Art-Tech congruency**.
- **Rule 2:** After applying Rule 1 and if there are proposals in the same position, priority will be given to proposals that have the highest score on **EC3. Technical capacities**.
- **Rule 3:** After applying Rule 2 and if there are proposals in the same position, priority will be given to proposals that have **applications with relevant social and environmental impact**.
- **Rule 4:** After applying Rule 3 and if there are proposals in the same position, priority will be given to earlier submitted proposals, which shall be selected first.

4.2.4. Step 4: Consensus meeting

Evaluators will carry out a consensus meeting with the objective of gathering their evaluations, defining a common score for the proposals, and preparing evaluation reports.

The evaluators will then hold a consensus meeting to prepare a single consensus Evaluation Summary Report (ESR) for each proposal, representing opinions and scores on which the evaluators agree and

which they will sign. The decision on the ranking list and on the selected applicants shall be sought by consensus, and whenever not feasible, by majority vote of 2/3.

4.2.5. Step 5: Proposals selection

The LAUDS OC#2 intends to provide support to at least eight (8) Experiments, expecting to select two (2) proposals per 3 LAUDS Factories and one (1) proposal per LAUDS Factories and at least one (1) proposal per domain. Nevertheless, the LAUDS Factories project reserves the right to decide differently on this distribution based on the quality of the proposals received.

The evaluators during the consensus meeting will prepare two lists:

- List of the selected projects: identification of the applications selected for funding.
- Reserve list: identification of the applications to be selected for funding, if any of those listed is unable to proceed to the implementation.

All applicants will be informed about the result of their evaluation by email **by 7 October 2025** (indicative date). The results will then be published on the information channels of the LAUDS project.

4.3. Redress process

Within three (3) working days of receiving (1) a Rejection Letter informing the proposal as noneligible or (2) an Evaluation Summary Report ranking the proposal below the selection borderline, an applicant may submit a request for redress if they believe the results of the eligibility checks have not been correctly applied, or if they feel that there has been a shortcoming in the way their proposal has been evaluated that may affect the final decision on whether to enter the funding program.

In such a case, an internal review committee from LAUDS will examine the applicant's request for a redress. The committee's role is to ensure a coherent interpretation of such requests, and equal treatment of applicants. Requests for redress must:

- Be related to the evaluation process or eligibility checks.
- Clearly describe the complaint.
- Received within the time limit (three (3) working days) from the reception of (1) a Rejection Letter considering the proposal as non-eligible or (2) the Evaluation Summary Report.
- Sent by the entity's legal representative that has also submitted the proposal.

The committee will review the complaint and will recommend an appropriate course of action. If there is clear evidence of a shortcoming that could affect the eventual funding decision, it is possible that all or part of the proposal will be re-evaluated. Please note:

- This procedure is concerned only with the general evaluation and/or eligibility checking process. The committee will not question the scientific or technical judgement of the evaluators.
- A re-evaluation will only be carried out if there is evidence of a shortcoming that affects the final decision on whether to fund the proposal or not. This means, for example, that a problem relating to one evaluation criterion will not lead to a re-evaluation if a proposal has failed anyway on other criteria.
- The evaluation score following any re-evaluation will be regarded as definitive. It may be lower than the original score.

All requests for redress will be treated in confidence and must be sent to the LAUDS team at lauds.opencall@inova.business.

In the case where a proposal under the redress process is re-evaluated and the new evaluation score is higher, it will be compared with the proposal that has entered the funding programme with the lowest ranking. The comparison will use the ranking rules as detailed in Step 4 (section 4.2.3). In case the proposal under the redress process ranks higher than both proposals will be invited to enter the funding programme.

4.4. Subprocess negotiation and onboarding

At the end of the evaluation phase, about eight (8) Experiments will be selected. The other proposals will remain on a reserve list in case a selected proposal fails to sign the sub-grant agreement. All proposals will receive an acceptance or rejection letter together with an anonymized version of their proposal Consensus Evaluation Report.

4.4.1. Step 1: Sub-grant agreement preparation

After the evaluation phase is concluded and the sub-projects are selected, the LAUDS consortium will start the SGA preparation phase in collaboration with the representatives of the sub-projects that have been awarded.

The objective of the SGA preparation is to fulfil the legal requirements between the LAUDS consortium and each beneficiary of the open call.

Request of the documentation:

- Proof of legal existence: Company(ies) register, official journal or other official document per country showing the name of the organisation(s), the legal address and registration number and a copy of a document proving VAT registration (in case the VAT number does not show on the registration extract or its equivalent).
- Proof of the SME/mid-cap condition is required:
 - If the applicant has been fully validated as an SME/mid-cap on the Beneficiary Register of the EC Participant Portal, the PIC number must be provided.
 - If the applicant has not been fully validated as an SME/mid-cap on the EC Participant Portal, the following documents will be required to prove the status as an SME/mid-cap:
 - a. SME/mid-cap declaration signed and stamped: If the beneficiary declares to be non-autonomous, the balance sheet and profit and loss account (with annexes) for the last period for upstream and downstream organizations is required.
 - b. Status Information Form, which includes the headcount (AWU), balance, profit & loss accounts of the latest closed financial year and the relation, upstream and downstream, of any linked or partner company.

The request of the documentation by the LAUDS consortium will be sent to the beneficiary, including deadlines by which information and documentation should be sent. In general, the SGA preparation should be concluded within two (2) weeks. An additional week may be provided by the LAUDS Project Coordinator in case of a relevant reasoning.

In case of the beneficiary not sending the requested documents within the above period, the proposal is automatically rejected and the next proposal in the reserve list is invited to initiate the contract preparation.

4.5. Step 2: Sub-grant Agreement signature

At the end of the Sub-grant Agreement (SGA) preparation phase, the SGA will be signed between the LAUDS consortium represented by its Coordinator (TUBerlin), the Host Organization (representing the LAUDS factory which will be determined according to the selected proposal) and the Beneficiary.

A model template for the contract will be provided by the LAUDS Factories project.

5. EXPECTED OUTPUTS OF SELECTED EXPERIMENTS

Selected Experiments shall implement activities addressing the challenges, objectives and requests mentioned in the LAUDS OC#2 *Call for Proposals*. Experiments will be asked to deliver at least the following outputs:

Output identification	Timing for delivery
1) one <i>challenge-focused report</i> describing the developed replication process including a blueprint of the proposed solution (where relevant);	First draft: 1 month before Experiment ends. Final version: At the end of the Experiment, at the closure meeting.
2) one <i>final report</i> on the collaboration with the LAUDS Factories Partners;	First draft: 1 month before Experiment ends. Final version: At the end of the Experiment, at the closure meeting.
3) <i>Photos, videos and social media content reporting the process, outputs and events implemented within the experiment. At least 10 photos, 2 short videos; 3 key short stories for social media (Instagram and LinkedIn);</i>	Along the Experiment implementation.
4) <i>A visual LAUDS Blueprint Canvas to document and communicate the process. The Blueprint is developed with the support of the communication coaches of SUPSI;</i>	Along the Experiment implementation.
5) <i>Feedback on Experiment's impact through short surveys and interviews;</i>	During last month of the Experiment.
6) <i>Participation in one LAUDS Factories event promoted within the project LAUDS Factories.</i>	Planned to occur by September 2026 (to be confirmed when Experiment starts).

Templates will be provided to selected Experiments.

6. OTHER RESPONSIBILITIES OF BENEFICIARIES

The selected hybrid team are indirectly beneficiaries of EC funding. Therefore, selected hybrid team members must comply with obligations under Horizon Europe specific requirements. The obligations that are applicable to the recipients include those described next.

6.1. Conflict of interest

The beneficiaries must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the sub-project is compromised for reasons involving economic interest, political or national affinity, family or emotional ties or any other shared interest ('conflict of interests').

They must formally notify the LAUDS consortium without delay of any situation constituting or likely to lead to a conflict of interests and immediately take all the necessary steps to rectify this situation. The LAUDS coordinator will verify if the measures taken are appropriate and may require additional measures to be taken by a specific deadline.

If the sub-contract consortium member breaches any of its obligations, the sub-contract may be automatically terminated.

6.2. Data protection and confidentiality

During implementation of the sub-project and for four years after the end of the sub-project, the parties must keep confidential any data, documents, or other material (in any form) that is identified as confidential at sub-contract signing time ('confidential information').

If a beneficiary requests it, the EC and the LAUDS consortium may agree to keep selected information confidential for an additional period beyond the initial four years. This will be explicitly stated in the sub-grant agreement.

If information has been identified as confidential during the sub-project implementation or only verbally, it will be confidential only if this is accepted by the LAUDS coordinator and confirmed in writing within fifteen (15) days of the verbal disclosure. Unless otherwise agreed between the parties, they may use confidential information only to implement the agreement.

The sub-project consortium may disclose confidential information to the LAUDS consortium and to the selected reviewers, who will be bound by a specific Non-Disclosure Agreement.

6.3. Promoting the action and giving visibility to the EU funding

The beneficiary must promote the sub-project, the LAUDS Factories project and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences in a strategic and effective manner and to highlight the financial support of the EC.

Unless the EC or the LAUDS coordinator agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible (requiring a valid justification), any promotion activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.), any publicity (including at a conference or seminar) or any type of information or promotional material (brochure, leaflet, poster, presentation etc.), and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the sub-grant must:

- display the EU emblem.

- display the LAUDS Factories logo.
- include the following text:
 - For communication activities: “The [sub-project acronym] has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe programme, via the LAUDS Open Call (OC2-2025-LAUDSREP-01) issued and executed under the LAUDS Factories project (Grant Agreement no. 101135986).”
 - For results publications: “This [insert type of result] is part of a sub-project that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe programme via an Open Call issued and executed under the LAUDS Factories project (Grant Agreement no. 101135986).”

When displayed in association with a logo, the European emblem should be given appropriate prominence. This obligation to use the European emblem in respect of projects to which the EC contributes implies no right of exclusive use. It is subject to general third-party use restrictions which do not permit the appropriation of the emblem, or of any similar trademark or logo, whether by registration or by any other means. Under these conditions, the beneficiary is exempted from the obligation to obtain prior permission from the EC to use the emblem. Further detailed information on the EU emblem can be found on the Europa web page⁶.

Any publicity made by the beneficiary regarding the sub-project, in whatever form and or by whatever medium, must specify that it reflects only the author’s views and that the EC or the LAUDS Factories project is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

The EC and the LAUDS consortium shall be authorised to publish, in whatever form and on or by whatever medium, the following information regarding the beneficiary/ies:

- The name of the beneficiary/ies.
- Contact address of the beneficiary/ies.
- The general purpose of the sub-project.
- The geographic location of the activities carried out.
- The list of dissemination activities relating to experiments.
- Any picture or any audio-visual or web material provided to the EC and LAUDS Factories project in the framework of the sub-project.

The beneficiary/ies shall ensure that all necessary authorisations for such publication have been obtained and that the publication of the information by the EC and LAUDS does not infringe any rights of third parties.

Upon a suitably justified request by the sub-project coordinator on behalf of any sub-project member, the LAUDS consortium, if permission is granted by the EC, may agree to forego such publicity if disclosure of the information indicated above would risk compromising the beneficiary’s security, academic or commercial interests.

⁶ https://european-union.europa.eu/principles-countries-history/symbols/european-flag_en#eu-emblem

7. CONTACT INFORMATION

If, after reading the Guide for Applicants and the FAQs on the call webpage, you have further questions regarding the Open Call process, please send us an email at lauds.opencall@inova.business.

The LAUDS consortium will provide information to the applicants via LAUDS Factories website, so that the information (question and answer) will be visible to all participants. No binding information will be provided via any other mean (e.g., telephone or email).

* In case of any technical issues, please include the following information in your message:

- your name and your email address;
- details of the specific problem (error messages you encountered, bugs descriptions, i.e. if a dropdown list isn't working, etc.);
- screenshots of the problem.

More info at the LAUDS Factories website: <https://lauds.eu/>

Apply via: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/lauds-call-2-replication>

LAUDS support team: lauds.opencall@inova.business

LAUDS OC#2 CALL:

CALL FOR PROPOSALS

GUIDE FOR APPLICANTS

CATALOGUE OF CHALLENGES

LAUDS FACTORIES CONSORTIUM PARTNERS

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT BERLIN / GRENOBLE INP-UGA / G-SCOP LABORATORY / UNIVERSITE
GRENOBLE ALPES / HSU – HELMUT-SCHMIDT UNIVERSITY / UNIVERSITY OF THE FEDERAL
ARMED FORCES HAMBURG / UNIVERSITÉ DE LORRAINE / ZENTRUM FÜR SOZIALE
INNOVATION GMBH / INOVA+, INNOVATION SERVICES, S.A / MAKER V-10 / STICHTING DYNE.
ORG / BAUHAUS-UNIVERSITÄT WEIMAR / FAB CITY HAMBURG E.V. / HIWW UG / FABLAB
DIGITAL FABRICATION AND OPEN INNOVATION LAB SUPSI / MEKANIKA / METALAB / TMDC

Co-funded by
the European Union

Annex 4: Application form

This annex replicates the specific open call proposal form that applicants have to complete and which can be found at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/lauds-call-2-replication>.

LAUDS Factories

OPEN CALL #2 | LAUDS Replication

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

Open Call #2 | LAUDS Replication

Call Kit available at: <https://lauds.eu/open-calls/2>

Please make sure you read all documentation before proceeding with your application submission.

The deadline for submitting proposals is **4 September 2025 at 17:00 (Central European Time)**.

In case of questions, please consult the Frequently Asked Questions section at LAUDS Open Call webpage: <https://lauds.eu/open-calls/2>

If you do not find answer to your questions in the documentation provided and FAQ section, please send us an email to: lauds.opencall@inova.business

Privacy & Data Protection: Data collected in this survey will be processed in accordance with the provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Data will be held secure and only available for as long as it is required by the LAUDS Factories project. The organisations composing the consortium of the LAUDS Factories will not make any unauthorised disclosure of this information and will only share it with other entities for the purpose of response analysis. Anonymised responses may be used as data for project publications and reports.

By submitting this form to the LAUDS Replication Open Call, you give your informed consent. If you have further questions, please contact the LAUDS Factories team: lauds.opencall@inova.business

Challenge Identification

* Which challenge is your proposal addressing?

- ⦿ Challenge A1: From Waste to Resource: Community-Driven Food Waste Valorisation Solutions [Host: Université de Lorraine]
- ⦿ Challenge A2: Advancing Urban Sustainability through Community-Based Green Education and Cultivation Systems [Host: METALAB]
- ⦿ Challenge A3: Local Production of Affordable and Sustainable Materials for Agriculture [Host: METALAB]
- ⦿ Challenge E1: Reimagining Energy Deliver Systems for Improved Autonomy and Resilience [Host: BUW]
- ⦿ Challenge E2: Democratizing Energy through DIY Renewable Energy Solutions [Host:TMDC]
- ⦿ Challenge E3: Reusing Fabrics and Advanced Biomaterials for Energy-Efficient Interiors [Host:SUPSI]
- ⦿ Challenge M1: Designing Effective Solutions for Active and Non-Motorized Transport [Host: BUW]
- ⦿ Challenge M2: Imaginative Solutions for Inclusive and Accesible Transportation [Host: SUPSI]
- ⦿ Challenge M3: Reducing Carbon Footprint of Urban Transport Systems [Host: TMDC]
- ⦿ Challenge M4: Innovative solutions for informed, accessible decision-making [Host: Université de Lorraine]

Proposal General Information

The information requested in this section will be used for public communication purposes if your application is selected for funding (e.g. communication in LAUDS website and social media).

*** Proposal Acronym:**

20 character(s) maximum

This information will be used for public communication purposes if your application is selected for funding (e.g. communication in LAUDS website and social media).

*** Proposal Full Title:**

200 character(s) maximum

This information will be used for public communication purposes if your application is selected for funding (e.g. communication in LAUDS website and social media).

*** Proposal Abstract:**

Please indicate the main objectives, methodology, activities to be performed, expected results, European added value.

2000 character(s) maximum

This information will be used for public communication purposes if your application is selected for funding (e.g. communication in LAUDS website and social media).

*** Proposal Keywords:**

(up to 6 keywords separated by ;):

This information will be used for public communication purposes if your application is selected for funding (e.g. communication in LAUDS website and social media).

*** Project duration (in months):**

Only values between 6 and 9 are allowed

This information will be used for public communication purposes if your application is selected for funding (e.g. communication in LAUDS website and social media).

*** Where will your Hybrid Team replicate the LAUDS models?**

Needs to be located within the European Union or Associated Countries

Needs to be located within the European Union or Associated Countries

This information will be used for public communication purposes if your application is selected for funding (e.g. communication in LAUDS website and social media).

Hybrid Team Presentation

If your application is selected for funding, we will use your organisation name, country and type (if technology provider, etc.) for public communication purposes (e.g. communication in LAUDS website and social media). If we need other information, we will ask you.

* Please indicate which type of entities compose the hybrid team presenting this proposal (select all that apply).

- Technology Provider
- Artist/Designer/Creative/Architect
- Other

If Other, please specify:

* Please indicate how many entities compose the hybrid team presenting this proposal.

- 2 3 4

Hybrid Team Leader | Entity Details

* Organisation Legal Name

* Type of Organisation

- Technology Provider
- Artist/Designer/Creative/Architect
- Other

If Other, please specify:

* Legal Statuses of Organisation

- Start-up
- Small- and Medium-sized Enterprise (SME)
- Mid-Cap
- Other

If Other, please specify:

* Full Address of Organisation

* Country of Organisation:

* VAT / TAX number of Organisation:

PIC number of organisation. In case your organisation has registered in EU Funding and Tenders portal, please provide the PIC number:

Learn more about PIC number here: <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/display/OM/Registration+and+validation+of+your+organisation>

* Webpage of Organisation

Hybrid Team Leader | Main Contact Information

* First and Last Name

* Position in the Organisation

* Gender

- Woman
- Man
- Non Binary
- Prefer not to say

* Email Address

Please ensure that the email address is correctly added, as this it will be the address used to communicate the results of your proposal.

* Phone Number (please add the country code, i.e., +xxx xxxxxxxx)

Hybrid Team Member | 2nd Entity Details

* Organisation Legal Name

* Type of Organisation

- Technology Provider
- Artist/Designer/Creative/Architect
- Other

If Other, please specify:

* Legal Statuses of Organisation

- Start-up
- Small- and Medium-sized Enterprise (SME)
- Mid-Cap
- Other

If Other, please specify:

* Full Address of Organisation

* Country of Organisation:

* VAT / TAX number of Organisation:

PIC number of organisation. In case your organisation has registered in EU Funding and Tenders portal, please provide the PIC number:

Learn more about PIC number here: <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/display/OM/Registration+and+validation+of+your+organisation>

* Webpage of Organisation

* Contact Person | First and Last Name

* Contact Person | Position in the Organisation

* Contact Person | Gender

- Woman
- Man
- Non Binary
- Prefer not to say

* Email Address

Please ensure that the email address is correctly added, as this it will be the address used to communicate the results of your proposal.

Hybrid Team Member | 3rd Entity Details

* Organisation Legal Name

* Type of Organisation

- Technology Provider

- Artist/Designer/Creative/Architect
- Other

If Other, please specify:

* Legal Statuses of Organisation

- Start-up
- Small- and Medium-sized Enterprise (SME)
- Mid-Cap
- Other

If Other, please specify:

* Full Address of Organisation

* Country of Organisation:

* Webpage of Organisation

* VAT / TAX number of Organisation:

PIC number of organisation. In case your organisation has registered in EU Funding and Tenders portal, please provide the PIC number:

Learn more about PIC number here: <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/display/OM/Registration+and+validation+of+your+organisation>

* Contact Person | First and Last Name

* Contact Person | Position in the Organisation

* Contact Person | Gender

- Woman
- Man
- Non Binary
- Prefer not to say

* Email Address

Please ensure that the email address is correctly added, as this it will be the address used to communicate the results of your proposal.

Hybrid Team Member | 4th Entity Details

* Organisation Legal Name

* Type of Organisation

- Technology Provider
- Artist/Designer/Creative/Architect
- Other

If Other, please specify:

* Legal Statutes of Organisation

- Start-up
- Small- and Medium-sized Enterprise (SME)
- Mid-Cap
- Other

If Other, please specify:

* Full Address of Organisation

* Country of Organisation:

* VAT / TAX number of Organisation:

PIC number of organisation. In case your organisation has registered in EU Funding and Tenders portal, please provide the PIC number:

Learn more about PIC number here: <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/display/OM/Registration+and+validation+of+your+organisation>

* Webpage of Organisation

* Contact Person | First and Last Name

* Contact Person | Position in the Organisation

* Contact Person | Gender

- Woman
- Man
- Non Binary
- Prefer not to say

* Email Address

Please ensure that the email address is correctly added, as this it will be the address used to communicate the results of your proposal.

Proposal Full Description

Download this template to prepare your technical annex and, after completing it, save it as a PDF file and upload it below.

[oc2-2025-LAUDSREP-01_TechnicalAnnex.docx](#)

Please upload your Technical Annex here:

Only files of the type pdf are allowed

Download this template to present your budget estimation and, after completing it, save it and upload it below.

Please upload your Budget file here:

Only files of the type pdf are allowed

Observations / additional comments

300 character(s) maximum

Declarations and consent

* We confirm having provided actual, correct and complete information in this application.

YES NO

* We confirm that to our best knowledge neither the proposal as a whole nor any parts of it have benefitted from any other EU grant. Please note that there is a strict prohibition of double funding from the EU budget.

YES NO

* We confirm we have read the Call Documentation and accept the terms and conditions described in these documents.

**Call documentation is composed of:*

- Call for Proposals
- Guidelines for Applicants
- Catalogue of Challenges

It is complemented with the:

- Sub-Grant Agreement
- Evaluation Guide for reviewers

which we recommend you to consult as well.

YES NO

* We confirm to be fully compliant with the eligibility criteria set out in the call.

**see the following sections of Guidelines for Applicants:*

- 3.1. Applications' eligibility
 - 3.1.1. Types of applicants
 - 3.1.2. Eligible Countries
 - 3.1.3. Conflict of interest
- 3.2. Proposal multiple submissions
- 3.3. Financial eligibility
- 3.4. Other Conditions

YES NO

* We confirm that we do not have any current or potential conflict of interest with the LAUDS Factories consortium or its Open Call process, as defined in the Guidelines for Applicants.

YES NO

* We confirm none of the members of the Hybrid Team is under liquidation or is an enterprise under difficulty according to the Commission Regulation No 651/2014, art. 2.18. Furthermore, we confirm we are not excluded from the possibility of obtaining EU funding under the provisions of both national and EU law, or by a decision of both national and EU authority.

YES NO

* We confirm the proposed project is based on original ideas and, going forward, none of the developments foreseen will be limited by third party rights, or are clearly stated in the proposal description if they are limited (including how they will be handled during the project). The project is based on work that has not been developed and offered as a commercial product or solution.

YES NO

* We are aware that if the proposal is retained for EU funding, we will be required to sign a declaration of honour and provide other supporting documents for an additional check on the eligibility and preparation of the sub-grant agreement.

YES NO

* We give our consent to participate in this application process. We understand that we can pull out of the application process (process comprising the phases before contract signature) at any time by sending an email to the Call Coordinators requesting that.

YES NO

* We give our consent to having our answers, contacts and application files stored, managed and analysed by LAUDS Factories Consortium members and Jury members for the purposes of LAUDS Factories Open Call #2 (LAUDS Replication).

YES NO

Disclaimer

LAUDS Factories is co-funded by the European Union.

The LAUDS Factories project (GA: 101135986) started on 01 January 2024 and has a duration of 36 months. More information available at <https://lauds.eu/>

Annex 5: Technical Annex

This annex is a Word template that indicates all the sections that must be completed as part of the technical proposal to be submitted. The sections are: i) Status of the Project, ii) Project objectives and activities, iii) Project Activities, Outputs and Cooperation, iv) Innovation potential and impact, v) Project Exploitation and Scale-Up, including communication and dissemination measures, vi) Team Competences and Expertise, vii) Additional pages for sketches/reference image (if any). The sections are aligned with the evaluation criteria. This is a mandatory annex to the proposal.

LAUDS Factories

TECHNICAL

ANNEX

LAUDS REPLICATION

OC2-2025-laudsrep-01

PROJECT IDENTIFICATION

Project Acronym: **Insert your project acronym here**

Project Title: **Insert your project title here**

Challenge: **Insert challenge identification here**

Applicant(s) Name(s): **Insert applicants' names here**

INSTRUCTIONS FOR THE TECHNICAL ANNEX

Use this template to prepare the Technical Annex of your proposal. The template structure, header and footer must not be modified.

The following formatting rules must be respected:

- **Maximum pages:** 6 pages (not including cover page) + 1 additional page for images/sketches (if any).
- **Font type:** Arial.
- **Font size:** body text shall have minimum 10 pts; tables/figures/footnotes can have minimum 9 pts. Any images, figures and tables must be readable.

Please delete this Instruction Page from your application.

After completing all sections in this Word document, convert it to a single PDF document (maximum size 10MB) and upload it to the LAUDS OC#2 Submission Form.

Disclaimer on Intellectual Property Rights and Copyright. LAUDS Factories strives to avoid the deliberate replication of ideas, data, results or other scientific or artistic work without due permission and acknowledgment. Make sure that the ideas developed in the proposal are yours (no plagiarism will be tolerated) and that you own or have received the necessary authorisations from the intellectual property rights holders to validly use, all intellectual property rights on the photographs, slides, graphs, digital images, or other material that you include in the Technical Annex.

Please delete this Instruction Page from your application before uploading it to LAUDS OC#2 Online Submission Form.

1. STATUS OF THE PROJECT

(Please indicate if the project has already been submitted to other programs or if it had some type of development already. Recommended maximum length: 0,25 pages characters)

Insert your text

2. PROJECT CONCEPT AND OBJECTIVES

(Please describe the objectives and approach that is behind your proposal. Recommended maximum length: 0,75 pages)

Insert your text

3. PROJECT ACTIVITIES, OUTPUTS AND COOPERATION

(Please describe the proposed activities, your intended work plan, including a timeline with a clear identification of the months and the activities to be performed and outputs to be delivered in each project period. Explain the planned cooperation and contribution of the elements of the consortium. Recommended maximum length: 1,5 pages)

Insert your text

4. INNOVATION POTENTIAL AND IMPACT

(Please clearly explain how the project is innovative, new, or experimental and/or how it can be exemplary for others. Describe the expected impact of your proposal at the local level, as well as at economic, environmental and social levels. Recommended maximum length: 1 page)

Insert your text

5. PROJECT EXPLOITATION AND SCALE-UP, INCLUDING COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION MEASURES

(Please describe the project potential for exploitation and scale-up, outlining your strategy to exploit and scale up the project. Detail here your communication and dissemination strategy and activities to support the project reaching the intended impact, exploitation and scale-up. Recommended maximum length: 1 page)

Insert your text

6. TEAM COMPETENCES AND EXPERTISE

(Please specify the team competences and skills and describe the capacity to carry out the proposed activities. Recommended maximum length: 1 page)

Insert your text

7. ADDITIONAL PAGES FOR SKETCHES / REFERENCE IMAGES (IF ANY)

(maximum length: 1 page)

Insert images

Annex 6: Budget Template

This annex is an Excel file to present a simplified estimation of costs for the implementation of the proposed project that should be provided as part of the application.

LAUDS Factories

Proposal Title
(please use the same title as the one inserted in the technical annex)

BUDGET ESTIMATION

Estimated eligible costs of the action and expected contribution

Cost Category	Estimated Eligible Cost	Justification <i>(provide details on the estimated costs)</i>
Personnel Costs		
Travel, accommodation and subsistence		
Equipment/Tech Consumables		
Other goods, works and services		
Subcontracting		
Indirect Costs (flat rate of 25% on direct costs)		
Total estimated costs	- €	

Estimated sources of financing of the action (revenue)

Requested contribution	
Own contribution	
Other sources	
Total estimated costs	- €

If applicable, please describe other sources:

Annex 7: Guidelines for Evaluators

This annex includes all the guidelines and instructions for evaluators. Also includes the template for Individual Evaluation Report.

LAUDS Factories

GUIDELINES

FOR

EVALUATORS

LAUDS REPLICATION

OC2-2025-laudsrep-01

CALL COORDINATOR:

INOVA+

Co-funded by
the European Union

LAUDS Factories is co-funded by the European Union (GA no. 101135986). Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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INTRODUCTION

This is the second Open Call for Experiments Proposals under the project **LAUDS Factories - Local Accessible Urban Digital and Sustainable Factories: New European Bauhaus Approach to Open and Decentralised Urban Manufacturing**¹, which is co-funded by the European Union.

LAUDS Factories is an innovative concept aiming at promoting and creating small, versatile factories in local and urban areas to co-create and produce customised products in small series.

The project aims to incorporate innovative and active resiliency capabilities at production and supply chain levels, as part of a green, circular, and digital transformation. The project seeks to create an increased personalised experience for customers, enhance their satisfaction and loyalty to local manufacturing businesses and, more generally, to boost local development of open and decentralised manufacturing ecosystems.

The Open Call #2 | LAUDS Replication will award 8 Experiments, proposed by hybrid teams, that replicate LAUDS models and adjust them to the contextual specificities, while answering to pressing challenges related to the mobility, energy and agriculture/food production sectors (see challenges detailed descriptions in the OC#2 - Catalogue of Challenges).

Consult all details on LAUDS OC#2 ambition in LAUDS OC#2 Call for Proposals.

1. OPEN CALL SELECTION PROCESS

Proposals submitted to the LAUDS Replication Open Call are submitted in a single stage and evaluated in two steps – remote evaluation and consensus meeting, as presented below:

An initial eligibility verification will be done by INOVA+ to filter out and discard non-eligible proposals. Proposals marked as non-eligible (for not meeting one or more of the eligibility criteria) will get a rejection

¹ Project website: <https://lauds.eu/>. Project on Cordis: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101135986/en>

letter with a justification. No additional feedback on the process will be given. Proposals considered eligible will move on to the evaluation phase.

1.1 Remote Evaluation

The remote evaluation will be done by senior experts from LAUDS partners organizations and external independent experts. The proposals will be scored based on the criteria below (Table 1).

Table 1 - LAUDS Replication Open Call evaluation criteria

Evaluation Criteria (EC)	Description
EC1. Technical approach & Art-Tech congruency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soundness of concept, quality of objectives and innovative elements of the proposal. Interaction with hosting LAUDS factory. • Quality and effectiveness of the work plan and outputs. • Synergy between members of the hybrid team will be assessed.
EC2. Innovation potential and impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Originality and novelty of presented ideas. • Relevance and credibility of the expected impacts of the proposed contribution, including at local, economic, environmental and social levels. • Quality of measures for exploitation and scale-up, including communication and dissemination actions.
EC3. Technical capacities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstration of competences and skills of the project team and its capacity to carry out the activities of the proposal. • Complementarity of partners.
EC4. Cost-benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adequacy of budget requested against the proposed workplan.

Each criterion will be scored between 0 and 5. Half point scores are not given. For each criterion under examination, score values will indicate the rationale presented next.

0	Fail	The proposal fails to address the criterion or cannot be judged due to incomplete or missing information.
1	Poor	The criterion is inadequately addressed or there are serious inherent weaknesses.
2	Fair	The proposal broadly addresses the criterion, but there are significant weaknesses.
3	Good	The proposal addresses the criterion well, but several shortcomings are present.
4	Very Good	The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but a small number of shortcomings are present.
5	Excellent	The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.

Each evaluator will record his/her individual assessment of each proposal using an Individual Evaluation Report (IER – see Annex 1).

>> Ranking of proposals

At the end of the remote external evaluation process, the final scores will be calculated. The final score of each application (including each criterion) is the average of the scores provided by evaluators.

Each criterion has a threshold, which is three (3). Any proposal receiving a score below 3 in any single criterion will be automatically rejected. Only proposals meeting or exceeding the minimum thresholds will advance in the competitive selection phase.

Proposals that successfully pass the threshold requirements will be ranked based on their overall score (sum of scores for criteria 1 to 4). Applications will be ranked in lists considering the following planned distribution:

- Two (2) proposals per three LAUDS Factories Hosts;
- One (1) challenge per two LAUDS Factories Hosts;
- A minimum of one (1) proposal from each domain.

Nevertheless, the LAUDS Factories Project reserves the right to decide differently on this distribution based on the quality of the proposals received.

In case of a tie, the following rules will apply:

- **Rule 1:** Priority will be given to proposals that have the highest score on **EC1. Technical approach & Art-Tech congruency**.
- **Rule 2:** After applying Rule 1 and if there are proposals in the same position, priority will be given to proposals that have the highest score on **EC3. Technical capacities**.
- **Rule 3:** After applying Rule 2 and if there are proposals in the same position, priority will be given to proposals that have **applications with relevant social and environmental impact**.
- **Rule 4:** After applying Rule 3 and if there are proposals in the same position, priority will be given to earlier submitted proposals, which shall be selected first.

1.2 Consensus Meeting

Evaluators will carry out a consensus meeting with the objective of gathering their evaluations, defining a common score for the proposals, and preparing evaluation reports.

The evaluators will then hold a consensus meeting to prepare a single consensus Evaluation Summary Report (ESR) for each proposal, representing opinions and scores on which the evaluators agree and which they will sign. The decision on the ranking list and on the selected applicants shall be sought by consensus, and whenever not feasible, by majority vote of 2/3.

>> Proposals selection

The LAUDS OC#2 intends to provide support to at least eight (8) Experiments, expecting to select two (2) proposals per 3 LAUDS Factories and one (1) proposal per LAUDS Factories and at least one (1) proposal per domain. Nevertheless, the LAUDS Factories project reserves the right to decide differently on this distribution based on the quality of the proposals received.

The evaluators during the consensus meeting will prepare two lists:

- List of the selected projects: identification of the applications selected for funding.

- Reserve list: identification of the applications to be selected for funding, if any of those listed is unable to proceed to the implementation.

2. CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Evaluators must immediately inform INOVA+ and the LAUDS Factories Coordinator when recognizing potential conflict of interest in the assessment of assigned proposals, in particular if:

- The evaluator has been involved in the preparation of an application.
- The evaluator benefit either directly or indirectly from the eventual selection of an application.
- The evaluator has a close family or personal relationship with any person representing the applicant.

3. CONFIDENTIALITY

Evaluators are required to treat information contained within applications with the strictest confidentiality and to declare any potential conflict of interest. Evaluators are responsible for ensuring and maintaining confidentiality of any data, documents or other material related to the evaluation process, during and after completion of the evaluation.

All evaluators are required to sign a Non-Conflict of Interest and Confidentiality Declaration (Annex 2) prior to accessing applicants' data.

ANNEX 1 – Individual Evaluation Report Template

Individual Evaluation Report

Evaluator Name

Evaluation Date

Challenge Identification

Proposal Title

Evaluation

	Fail (0)	Poor (1)	Fair (2)	Good (3)	Very Good (4)	Excellent (5)
EC1. Technical approach & Art-Tech congruency						
EC2. Innovation potential and impact						
EC3. Technical capacities						
EC4. Cost-benefit						

Final Evaluation

Observations

ANNEX 2 – Non-Conflict of Interest and Confidentiality Declaration

Declaration on Non-Conflict of Interest and Confidentiality

CALL: OC2-2025-LAUDSREP-01 | LAUDS REPLICATION

The undersigned, **(insert name of the signatory of this form)**, from **(partner organisation)**, declares that in his/her role as a member of the jury panel, he/she will carefully analyse the absence of conflict of interests in connection with the applications to be assessed. A conflict of interests could arise in particular as a result of economic interests, family, emotional life, or any other shared interest. The reasons that can lead to such conflict of interest might include, for example, working at the same institution as the applicant or having performed previous services to or together with the applicant.

In case of any conflict of interests, he/she will inform the LAUDS Factories consortium. In that case(s), he/she will not participate in the assessment of the application(s) connected with the conflict of interests.

Moreover, he/she commits to not disclose any information that he/she has access to for the execution of the evaluation process, which must be a priori considered as confidential, including contents of applications, exchanges between jury members and results of the overall selection process.

Name / Entity	
Date	
Signature	

LAUDS FACTORIES CONSORTIUM PARTNERS

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT BERLIN / GRENOBLE INP-UGA / G-SCOP LABORATORY / UNIVERSITE
GRENOBLE ALPES / HSU – HELMUT-SCHMIDT UNIVERSITY / UNIVERSITY OF THE FEDERAL
ARMED FORCES HAMBURG / UNIVERSITÉ DE LORRAINE / ZENTRUM FÜR SOZIALE
INNOVATION GMBH / INOVA+, INNOVATION SERVICES, S.A / MAKER V-10 / STICHTING DYNE.
ORG / BAUHAUS-UNIVERSITÄT WEIMAR / FAB CITY HAMBURG E.V. / HIWW UG / FABLAB
DIGITAL FABRICATION AND OPEN INNOVATION LAB SUPSI / MEKANIKA / METALAB / TMDC

Co-funded by
the European Union

Annex 8: Sub-grant Agreement Template

This annex is a template of the sub-grant agreement (contract) that will be signed by all parties (LAUDS Factories Project Coordinator (as Contractor), the Host Organization and the beneficiary). It describes all the rights and responsibilities of the signing parties.

Local Accessible Urban Digital and Sustainable Factories: New European Bauhaus Approach to Open and Decentralised Urban Manufacturing

#2 OPEN CALL | LAUDS REPLICATION

SUB-GRANT AGREEMENT

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#2 OPEN CALL | LAUDS REPLICATION**Subject:** Sub-Grant Agreement (SGA)**Call:** oc2-2025-LAUDSREP-01**Sub-Grant Agreement n°:** *internal reference of the project approved.***Title of the Experiment:** *name of the project approved.*

The following Parties:

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT BERLIN (TUB) – LAUDS Factories' Project Coordinator

and

INSTITUT POLYTECHNIQUE DE GRENOBLE (GINP), HELMUT SCHMIDT UNIVERSITÄT UNIVERSITÄT DER BUNDESWEHR HAMBURG (HSU), UNIVERSITÉ DE LORRAINE (UL), ZENTRUM FÜR SOZIALE INNOVATION GMBH (ZSI), INOVA+ - INNOVATION SERVICES, SA (INOVA), MAKER (MAK), Mekanika SRL (MEK), Taller para la Materialización y Desarrollo de Conceptos (TMDC), NON-GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATION METALAB (MLAB), STICHTING DYNE. ORG (DYNE), BAUHAUS-UNIVERSITÄT WEIMAR (BUW), FAB CITY HAMBURG EV (FCHH), HIWW HAMBURGER INSTITUT FÜR WERTSCHWERTSCHOPFUNGSSYSTEMATIK UND WISSENSMANAGEMENT UG (HAFTUNGSBESCHRÄNKT) (HIWW) - Consortium partners all hereinafter jointly referred as Consortium/Consortium partners.

The Consortium of the **LAUDS Factories - Local Accessible Urban Digital and Sustainable Factories: New European Bauhaus Approach to Open and Decentralised Urban Manufacturing**¹ project is represented for the purpose of signing this SGA by:

- the **Project Coordinator TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT BERLIN (TUB)**, with legal address at Strasse des 17 Juni 135, Berlin 10623, Germany, VAT number: [.....] (*hereinafter referred to as the CONTRACTOR*)
- and by the **LAUDS Factory, [Name of the Entity]**, legal entity organized under the laws of [country], with its registered office at [.....], [Country], with VAT number [.....] (*hereinafter referred to as the HOST*);

and

the hybrid team of the [name of the project selected] selected in the #2 OPEN CALL | LAUDS REPLICATION (oc2-2025-LAUDSREP-01) and described in the application form submitted in the above-mentioned Open Call, which is composed by:

- [Name of the Entity], legal entity organized under the laws of [country], with its registered office at [.....], [Country], with VAT number [.....], represented by [name, surname and position],
- and [Name of the Entity], legal entity organized under the laws of [country], with its registered office at [.....], [Country], with VAT number [.....], represented by [name, surname and position]

¹ Grant agreement n° 101135986, funded by the European Union through the European Commission programme Horizon Europe.

(hereinafter referred to as the BENEFICIARY).

[if additional entities form the consortium, information about each of the participating entities should be included]

Hereinafter, CONTRACTOR, HOST and BENEFICIARY each individually referred to as a PARTY and collectively as Parties,

have agreed to enter into agreement with the terms and conditions below, including those in the following annexes, which form an integral part of this Sub-Grant Agreement.

TERMS AND CONDITIONS

ARTICLE 1. Subject of the Sub-Grant Agreement

This Sub-Grant Agreement (SGA) sets out the rights and obligations and the terms and conditions applicable to the grant awarded to the Beneficiary for implementing the Experiment set out in Article 2. By signing the SGA, the Beneficiary accepts the grant and agrees to implement the Experiment, acting on their responsibility.

The present SGA does not create a joint-venture company and under no circumstances be considered as a holding between the parties. The responsibility of each Party is strictly limited to the conditions mentioned in this SGA, particularly the conditions of take by each Party to any other third party.

ARTICLE 2. Entry into force, implementation period and termination

The grant is awarded for the Experiment entitled **["name of the project selected"]**, as described in Annex 1 – Description of the Experiment.

The Experiment runs for **## months** starting on a fixed date, **DD/MONTH/YYYY**, when the SGA enters into force.

The Beneficiary may apply for an extension (up to a maximum of one month as the total duration) of the Experiment Period if there are objective conditions which prevent its implementation in time. The Beneficiary's request should indicate the circumstances justifying the extension and the period for which the project should be extended. The circumstances of extension will be assessed by the Selection Committee.

The SGA will end upon one of the following conditions:

- after delivery of all expected outcomes specified in Annex 1 – Description of the Experiment and final payment by the Contractor. The foreseen date of completion is **[XXX]**.
- in the case of termination initiated by the Contractor in the conditions specified in Article 4. In this case, no other payment will be due by the Contractor to the Beneficiary and all Parties give up any pursuit exercised against one or several other Parties for a direct or indirect damage incurred by the partial or total non-fulfillment of the measures of the present SGA.

ARTICLE 3. Obligations and Responsibilities

3.1 Obligations and Responsibilities of the Contractor

The Contractor, or another partner of the LAUDS Factories project nominated by it, will monitor the execution of the Experiment, acknowledge receipt and validate the content of the planned deliverables.

The Contractor will also manage the related payments to the Beneficiary with a maximum delay of 45 days after validation.

3.2 Obligations and Responsibilities of the Host

The Host will provide the Beneficiary, within the limits of the needs of the Experiment, with the elements of the LAUDS Factory in the forms and at deadlines conformant to the workplan and will assist Beneficiary in documenting the Experiment.

It will also provide the Beneficiary with the foreseen hosting infrastructure and resources as described in the #2 Open Call | LAUDS Replication (oc2-2025-LAUDSREP-01) and described in Annex 2 - Open Call Documentation. It undertakes to make its best efforts to assure the success of the Experiment.

3.3 Obligations and Responsibilities of the Beneficiary

The obligations and responsibilities of the Beneficiary are defined in detail in Annex 1 - Description of the Experiment, and the Annex 2 - Open Call Documentation.

By signing this SGA, the Beneficiary declares they meet the eligibility conditions for participation in LAUDS Exploration initiative, as defined in the #2 Open Call | LAUDS Replication (oc2-2025-LAUDSREP-01) as detailed in the Guidelines for Applicants.

The Beneficiary shall take every necessary precaution to avoid any risk of conflict of interest relating to economic interests, political or national affinities, personal or any other interests liable to influence the impartial and objective performance of the Experiment. In case the Beneficiary is involved in a conflict of interest or in a risk of conflict of interest, the Beneficiary must formally notify this situation to the Contractor without delay and immediately take all the necessary steps to rectify this situation.

The Beneficiary is responsible for any act or omission that causes damage to the Contractor, other partner of LAUDS Factories consortium members, and/or the EC in relation to this SGA. The Beneficiary shall bear sole responsibility for ensuring that their acts within the framework of this SGA do not infringe on third parties' rights. Neither the Contractor, the Host nor the EC can be held liable for any acts or omissions of the Beneficiary in relation to this SGA.

ARTICLE 4. Breach of Contractual Obligations

In the event of the breach of the contractual obligations by the Beneficiary, the Contractor reserves the right to claim the Beneficiary the full refund of all payments made to the Beneficiary up to date.

The breach of the contractual obligations by the Beneficiary shall be determined by the Contractor. Not participation in the activities foreseen for the implementation of the Experiment (unless in the case of Force Majeure) or participating in them in a manner which intentionally disrupts the expected outcomes, shall be deemed as breach of the contractual obligations by the Beneficiary.

The provision of false or misleading declarations by the Beneficiary or any unsolved situation of conflict of interest also constitute examples of breach of contractual obligations by the Beneficiary.

ARTICLE 5. Grant and Financial Provisions

5.1 Maximum grant

The maximum grant amount provided by the Contractor to the Beneficiary is EUR xxxxxx (xxxxxx) Euros paid as a lump sum following the conditions set out in this SGA and its Annexes.

5.2 Payment of the grant

Payment of the grant amount will be made in three payments in the form of a lump sum, intended to support the Beneficiary's implementation of the activities, including personnel costs, travel costs, equipment/tech consumables costs (depreciation) and, whenever required, overheads and subcontracting.

Payment Schedule: The first payment (40%) with the SGA signature, a second payment (40%) with an interim assessment, and then the remaining amount (20%) after the completion of the activities, with the achievement of agreed milestones and deliverables.

The Beneficiary is responsible for complying with any tax and legal obligations that might be attached to this financial contribution.

The hybrid team of the *["name of the project selected"]* nominates *["Name of the Entity"]* as the leader of the consortium and recipient of the funds, which will receive the payment from the Contractor and is responsible for the distribution among the hybrid team members. All payments shall be made to the Beneficiary's bank account, denominated in euros, as indicated in Annex 3 – Bank Account Information.

The cost of payment transfers will be borne as follows:

- the Contractor bears the cost of transfers charged by its bank;
- the Beneficiary bears the cost of transfers charged by its bank;
- the party causing a repetition of a transfer bears all costs of the repeated transfer.

5.3 Suspension of payment of the grant

The Contractor may at any moment suspend, in whole or in part, the pre-financing payment, the interim payment or the payment of the balance for the Beneficiary:

- if the Contractor has evidence that the Beneficiary has committed irregularities, fraud or breach of obligations in the award procedure or while implementing the SGA;
- if the Contractor has evidence that the Beneficiary has committed systemic or recurrent irregularities, fraud or serious breach of obligations in other grants funded by the European Union awarded to the beneficiary under similar conditions and such irregularities, fraud or breach of obligations have a material impact on this grant; or
- if the Contractor suspects irregularities, fraud or breach of obligations committed by the Beneficiary in the award procedure or while implementing the SGA and needs to verify whether they have actually occurred.

Before suspending payments, the Contractor must send a formal notification to the Beneficiary informing them of its intention to suspend payments; the reasons for suspension; and, when applicable, the conditions that need to be met for payments to resume; inviting the Beneficiary to submit observations within 30 calendar days of receiving the formal notification.

If the Contractor does not receive observations or decides to pursue the procedure despite the observations it has received, it must send a formal notification to the Beneficiary informing them of the suspension of payments; the reasons for suspension; the final conditions under which payments may resume; and, when applicable, the indicative date of completion of the necessary verification.

The suspension takes effect on the day the Contractor sends formal notification of suspension.

Otherwise, the Contractor must send a formal notification to the Beneficiary informing them that it is not continuing with the suspension procedure.

During the period of suspension of payments, the Beneficiary is not entitled to submit any request for payments nor supporting documents. The corresponding request for payments and supporting documents may be

submitted as soon as possible after the resumption of payments or may be included in the first request for payment due following the resumption of payments.

The suspension of payments does not affect the right of the Contractor to suspend the implementation of the Experiment or to terminate the SGA.

In order for the Contractor to resume payments, the Beneficiary must meet the notified conditions as soon as possible and must inform the Contractor of any progress made. If the conditions for resuming payments are met, the suspension will be lifted. The Contractor will send a formal notification to the Beneficiary informing them of this.

5.4 Use of the grant amount and recovery

The Beneficiary commits to the proper use of the funding, for the purposes of carrying out the #2 Open Call | LAUDS Replication (oc2-2025-LAUDSREP-01), in compliance with its description reflected in Annex 1, and in accordance with Annex 2 – Open Call Documentation.

If, based on an audit, the EC seeks to recover contributions from the Contractor of financial contributions made to the Beneficiary under this SGA, due to misuse of the funding received, the Beneficiary agrees to repay such amounts to the Contractor.

ARTICLE 6. Insurances

All Parties shall take out adequate insurance of all risks associated with the travels undertaken in the scope of the implementation of the Experiment, and for any piece of equipment they will bring respectively into the implementation of the activities within the *["name of the project selected"]*.

ARTICLE 7. Confidentiality and Ethics

During the implementation of the Experiment and for five years after the final payment, the parties must treat with confidentiality any confidential information and documents. The parties must handle classified information in accordance with the applicable EU, international or national law on classified information (in particular, Decision 2015/444 and its implementing rules).

The parties may only use confidential information and documents for a reason other than to fulfil their obligations under the SGA if they have first obtained the prior written agreement of the other party.

The Beneficiary may disclose sensitive information to their personnel or other participants involved in the Experiment only if they need to know it in order to implement the SGA and are bound by an obligation of confidentiality.

The confidentiality obligations no longer apply if:

- the disclosing party agrees to release the other party;
- the information becomes publicly available, without breaching any confidentiality obligation;
- the disclosure of sensitive information is required by EU, international or national law.

The Experiment must be carried out in line with the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles.

ARTICLE 8. Intellectual Property Rights

8.1 General principles

The Beneficiary must inform the Contractor and the Host about background data, know-how or information — whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any rights such as intellectual property rights — that is held by the Beneficiary before they acceded to the SGA and needed to implement the Experiment or exploit the results. If the background is subject to the rights of a third party, the Beneficiary must ensure that it is able to comply with its obligations under the SGA.

The Contractor has the right to use non-sensitive information relating to the Experiment and materials and documents received from the beneficiaries (notable summaries for publication, deliverables, as well as any other material, such as pictures or audio-visual material, in paper or electronic form) for information, communication, dissemination and publicity purposes during the Experiment or afterwards.

8.2 Ownership of the data

The ownership of the data provided by the any entity from LAUDS Factories consortium, including the Host, or any other data source or provider will be always from the Party providing the data.

The Contractor does not obtain ownership of the results produced under the Experiment. If the Experiment results in the generation of data, the ownership of the generated data will be always from the Party generating the data, unless the Parties agree any specification.

‘Results’ means any tangible or intangible effect of the Experiment, such as data, know-how or information, whatever its form or nature, whether or not it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights.

ARTICLE 9. Data Protection

Any personal data under the SGA will be processed under the responsibility of the data controller of the Contractor in accordance with the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons concerning the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.

The Beneficiary must process personal data under the SGA in compliance with the applicable EU, international and national law on data protection (in particular, Regulation 2016/67919). The Beneficiary must ensure that personal data is:

- processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subjects;
- collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes;
- adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed;
- accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date;
- kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the data is processed and;
- processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the data.

The Beneficiary may grant their personnel access to personal data only if it is strictly necessary for implementing, managing, and monitoring the SGA, but must ensure that the personnel is under a confidentiality obligation.

ARTICLE 10. Dissemination, Visibility and Compulsory Credits

The Beneficiary must promote the Experiment and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences, in accordance with the Description of the Experiment (Annex 1) and in a strategic, coherent, and effective manner.

All Parties shall include, if possible, on each publication or communication (print and/or multimedia) related to the public presentation of the results of the #2 Open Call | LAUDS Replication (oc2-2025-LAUDSREP-01), the following mention:

*“The **NAME_of_Project_Selected** has received funding from the European Union, via the oc2-2025-LAUDSREP-01 issued and implemented by the LAUDS Factories project, under the grant agreement No 101135986.”*

Communication activities of the Beneficiary related to the Experiment (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any equipment, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge the EU support and display the European flag (emblem), funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate) and must indicate that it reflects only the author’s view; and that the Contractor, the Host or the European Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Where appropriate, they should also use the LAUDS Factories project visuals, in line with the Guidelines provided by the Contractor.

When displayed in association with another logo, the European Union emblem must have appropriate prominence.

The obligation to display the European Union emblem does not confer on the beneficiaries a right of exclusive use. The beneficiaries may not appropriate the European Union emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

The Contractor and the EC shall be authorized to publish, in whatever form and on or by whatever medium, the following information:

- the name of the Beneficiary;
- contact address of the Beneficiary;
- the general purpose of the Experiment;
- the amount of the financial contribution of the EC.

ARTICLE 11. Amendments

Any amendment to the SGA must be made in writing. An amendment may not have the purpose or the effect of making changes to the SGA which would call into question the decision awarding the grant or be contrary to the equal treatment of applicants.

Any request for amendment must be duly justified, be accompanied by appropriate supporting documents; be made in writing and signed by the duly authorized representative of the Contracting Parties.

In the event the European Commission modifies the conditions on which the Open Call has been issued, the Contractor will amend the SGA accordingly.

ARTICLE 12. Force Majeure

This SGA will be revoked as right and without compensation of any kind in all cases of *force majeure* recognized by the law and case law (natural disaster, strike, national mourning, riots, terrorism acts, war, epidemic, etc.).

A party faced with *force majeure* must send a formal notification to the other party without delay, stating the nature of the situation or of the event, its likely duration and foreseeable effects.

The parties must take the necessary measures to limit any damage due to *force majeure*. They must do their best to resume the implementation of the Experiment as soon as possible.

ARTICLE 13. Language

This SGA is drawn in English, language that shall govern all documents, notices, meetings and processes relative thereto.

ARTICLE 14. Attribution of Jurisdiction

In case of any dispute concerning the execution of this SGA, the partners agree to submit to the Court of Brussels, Belgium.

ARTICLE 15. Governing Law

The SGA is governed by its terms, the Union law applicable, and, on a subsidiary basis, by the law of Belgium.

SIGNATURES

The Parties have caused this SGA to be duly signed by the undersigned authorized representatives in four (4) copies:

For LAUDS Factories Project - CONTRACTOR

[Insert forename, surname, position]

For LAUDS Factory (name) - HOST

[Insert forename, surname, position]

For the BENEFIARY

[Insert forename, surname]

For the BENEFICIARY

[Insert forename, surname]

Done at [insert date DD/MM/YYYY] on [insert city and country]

ANNEX 1 – Description of Experiment

[This refers to the proposal submitted and selected after introducing the changes, if any, during the negotiation of the SGA].

ANNEX 2 – Open Call Documentation

[This refers to the Guidelines for Applicants and Catalogue of Challenges published by the time the open call is open].

ANNEX 3 – Bank Account Information

[This refers to the Bank Account Information template filled in and duly signed by the Beneficiary and the Bank representative].

ANNEX 4 – Declaration of Honour

[This refers to the declaration(s) of honour submitted with the proposal in the application phase].

Annex 9: Declaration of Honour

This annex must be signed by legal entities submitting a proposal, which declare that all conditions of the open call are accepted by the entity's legal representative.

Declaration on honour on exclusion criteria and selection criteria

The undersigned [*insert name of the signatory of this form*], representing:

<i>(only for natural persons)</i> himself or herself	<i>(only for legal persons)</i> the following legal person:
ID or passport number: ('the person')	Full official name: Official legal form: Statutory registration number: Full official address: VAT registration number: ('the person')

I – Situation of exclusion concerning the person

	YES	NO
(1) declares that the above-mentioned person is in one of the following situations:		
(a) it is bankrupt, subject to insolvency or winding-up procedures, its assets are being administered by a liquidator or by a court, it is in an arrangement with creditors, its business activities are suspended or it is in any analogous situation arising from a similar procedure provided for under Union or national law;		
(b) it has been established by a final judgement or a final administrative decision that the person is in breach of its obligations relating to the payment of taxes or social security contributions in accordance with the applicable law;		
(c) it has been established by a final judgement or a final administrative decision that the person is guilty of grave professional misconduct by having violated applicable laws or regulations or ethical standards of the profession to which the person belongs, or by having engaged in any wrongful conduct which has an impact on its professional credibility where such conduct denotes wrongful intent or gross negligence, including, in particular, any of the following:		
(i) fraudulently or negligently misrepresenting information required for the verification of the absence of grounds for exclusion or the fulfilment of eligibility or selection criteria or in the performance of a contract or an agreement;		
(ii) entering into agreement with other persons with the aim of distorting competition;		
(iii) violating intellectual property rights;		
(iv) attempting to influence the decision-making process of the during the award procedure;		

(v) attempting to obtain confidential information that may confer upon it undue advantages in the award procedure;		
(d) it has been established by a final judgement that the person is guilty of any of the following:		
(i) fraud, within the meaning of Article 3 of Directive (EU) 2017/1371 and Article 1 of the Convention on the protection of the European Communities' financial interests, drawn up by the Council Act of 26 July 1995;		
(ii) corruption, as defined in Article 4(2) of Directive (EU) 2017/1371 or active corruption within the meaning of Article 3 of the Convention on the fight against corruption involving officials of the European Communities or officials of Member States of the European Union, drawn up by the Council Act of 26 May 1997, or conduct referred to in Article 2(1) of Council Framework Decision 2003/568/JHA, as well as corruption as defined in other applicable laws;		
(iii) conduct related to a criminal organisation, as referred to in Article 2 of Council Framework Decision 2008/841/JHA;		
(iv) money laundering or terrorist financing, within the meaning of Article 1(3), (4) and (5) of Directive (EU) 2015/849 of the European Parliament and of the Council;		
(v) terrorist offences or offences linked to terrorist activities, as defined in Articles 1 and 3 of Council Framework Decision 2002/475/JHA, respectively, or inciting, aiding, abetting or attempting to commit such offences, as referred to in Article 4 of that Decision;		
(vi) child labour or other offences concerning trafficking in human beings as referred to in Article 2 of Directive 2011/36/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council;		
(e) it has shown significant deficiencies in complying with the main obligations in the performance of a contract or an agreement financed by the Union's budget, which has led to its early termination or to the application of liquidated damages or other contractual penalties, or which has been discovered following checks, audits or investigations by a contracting authority, the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF) or the Court of Auditors;		
(f) it has been established by a final judgment or final administrative decision that the person has committed an irregularity within the meaning of Article 1(2) of Council Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 2988/95;		
(g) it has been established by a final judgment or final administrative decision that the person has created an entity under a different jurisdiction with the intent to circumvent fiscal, social or any other legal		

obligations in the jurisdiction of its registered office, central administration or principal place of business.		
(h) it has been established by a final judgment or final administrative decision that the person has been created with the intent provided for in point (g).		
(i) for the situations referred to in points (c) to (h) above the person is subject to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. facts established in the context of audits or investigations carried out by the European Public Prosecutor's Office after its establishment, the Court of Auditors, the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF) or the internal auditor, or any other check, audit or control performed under the responsibility of an authorising officer of an EU institution, of a European office or of an EU agency or body; ii. non-final judgments or non-final administrative decisions which may include disciplinary measures taken by the competent supervisory body responsible for the verification of the application of standards of professional ethics; iii. facts referred to in decisions of entities or persons being entrusted with EU budget implementation tasks; iv. information transmitted by Member States implementing Union funds; v. decisions of the Commission relating to the infringement of Union competition law or of a national competent authority relating to the infringement of Union or national competition law; or vi. decisions of exclusion by an authorising officer of an EU institution, of a European office or of an EU agency or body. 		

II – Situations of exclusion concerning natural or legal persons with power of representation, decision-making or control over the legal person and beneficial owners

Not applicable to natural persons, Member States and local authorities

(2) declares that a natural or legal person who is a member of the administrative, management or supervisory body of the above-mentioned legal person, or who has powers of representation, decision or control with regard to the above-mentioned legal person (this covers e.g. company directors, members of management or supervisory bodies, and cases where one natural or legal person holds a majority of shares), or a beneficial owner of the person (as referred to in point 6 of article 3 of Directive (EU) No 2015/849) is in one of the following situations:	YES	NO	N/A
Situation (c) above (grave professional misconduct)			

Situation (d) above (fraud, corruption or other criminal offence)			
Situation (e) above (significant deficiencies in performance of a contract)			
Situation (f) above (irregularity)			
Situation (g) above (creation of an entity with the intent to circumvent legal obligations)			
Situation (h) above (person created with the intent to circumvent legal obligations)			
Situation (i) above			

III – Situations of exclusion concerning natural or legal persons assuming unlimited liability for the debts of the legal person

(3) declares that a natural or legal person that assumes unlimited liability for the debts of the above-mentioned legal person is in one of the following situations:	YES	NO	N/A
Situation (a) above (bankruptcy)			
Situation (b) above (breach in payment of taxes or social security contributions)			

IV – Grounds for rejection from this procedure

(4) declares that the above-mentioned person:	YES	NO
Was previously involved in the preparation of the call documents used in this award procedure, where this entailed a breach of the principle of equality of treatment including distortion of competition that cannot be remedied otherwise.		

V – Remedial measures

If the person declares one of the situations of exclusion listed above, it must indicate measures it has taken to remedy the exclusion situation, thus demonstrating its reliability. This may include e.g. technical, organisational and personnel measures to prevent further occurrence, compensation of damage or payment of fines or of any taxes or social security contributions. The relevant documentary evidence which illustrates the remedial measures taken must be provided in annex to this declaration. This does not apply for situations referred in point (d) of this declaration.

VI – Evidence upon request

Upon request and within the time limit set by the contracting authority the person must provide information on natural or legal persons that are members of the administrative, management or supervisory body or that have powers of representation, decision or control, including legal and natural persons within the ownership and control structure and beneficial owners.

It must also provide the following evidence concerning the person itself and the natural or legal persons on whose capacity the person intends to rely, or a subcontractor and concerning the natural or legal persons which assume unlimited liability for the debts of the person:

- For situations described in (a), (c), (d), (f), (g) and (h), production of a recent extract from the judicial record is required or, failing that, an equivalent document recently issued by a judicial or administrative authority in the country of establishment of the person showing that those requirements are satisfied.
- For the situation described in point (b), production of recent certificates issued by the competent authorities of the State concerned are required. These documents must provide evidence covering all taxes and social security contributions for which the person is liable, including for example, VAT, income tax (natural persons only), company tax (legal persons only) and social security contributions. Where any document described above is not issued in the country concerned, it may be replaced by a sworn statement made before a judicial authority or notary or, failing that, a solemn statement made before an administrative authority or a qualified professional body in its country of establishment.

VII – Selection criteria

(1) declares that the above-mentioned person complies with the selection criteria applicable to it individually as provided in the call specifications:	YES	NO	N/A
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The above-mentioned person must immediately inform the LAUDS Factories consortium of any changes in the situations as declared.

The above-mentioned person may be subject to rejection from this procedure and to administrative sanctions (exclusion or financial penalty) if any of the declarations or information provided as a condition for participating in this procedure prove to be false.

Full name

Date

Signature

Annex 10: SME Declaration Form

This annex must be signed by SMEs presenting proposals, stating that all the conditions specified by the European Commission in the definition of SME are fulfilled.

Small and Medium Enterprise (SME) Declaration Form

IDENTIFICATION OF THE APPLICANT ENTREPRISE

Name or Business Name	
Address (of registered office)	
Registration / VAT Number	

The [European Commission definition](#) states that “the category of micro, small and medium enterprises (SMEs) is made up of enterprises which employ fewer than 250 persons and which have an annual turnover not exceeding EUR 50 million, and/or annual balance sheet total not exceeding EUR 43 million. Within the SME category, a small enterprise is defined as an enterprise which employs fewer than 50 persons and whose annual turnover and/or balance sheet total does not exceed EUR 10 million and a micro enterprise is defined as an enterprise which employs fewer than 10 persons and whose annual turnover and/or annual balance sheet total does not exceed EUR 2 million”.

Data¹ used to determine the type of company

Calculated according to Article 6 of the Annex to the Commission Recommendation 2003/361/EC on the SME definition.

Autonomous Enterprise ²	Headcount (AWU)	Reference period	Annual turnover (million €)
YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>			

I declare on my honour the accuracy of this declaration and, I hereby, certify that **[name of enterprise]** fulfils the criteria as stipulated in the [European Commission definition](#).

Signature

Name and position of the signatory, being authorised to the represent the enterprise

Place and date

¹ Data are those relating to the latest approved accounting period and calculated on an annual basis. They are considered from the date of closure of the accounts. The amount selected for the turnover is calculated excluding value added tax (VAT). In the case of newly established enterprises whose accounts have not yet been approved, the data to apply is to be derived from a bona fide estimate made over the financial year.

² An “autonomous enterprise” is any enterprise which is not owned as to 25% or more by one enterprise or jointly by enterprises linked to one another. For more details and specific cases, refer to the European Commission Recommendation (2003/361/EC)

Annex 11: Bank Account Information

This annex is an administrative document that collects information about the bank account to which payments to beneficiaries will be made.

Bank Account Information

ACCOUNT HOLDER INFORMATION

Account Name Holder <i>The name or title under which the account has been opened and NOT the name of the authorized agent</i>	
Holder's Address	
Postcode	
Town/City	
Country	

Contact Person <i>It does not need to be an authorised agent.</i>	
Telephone	

BANK ACCOUNT INFORMATION

Bank Name	
Branch Address	
Postcode	
Town/City	
Country	
IBAN number / Account number <i>Format example: ES76 2077 0024 0031 0257 5766</i>	
SWIFT code <i>8 to 11 characters</i>	

Bank Stamp + Signature of Bank Representative <i>Can be substituted by the attachment of a recent bank statement (less than 2 months).</i>	Date + Signature of Account Holder <i>(Mandatory)</i>
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Technische Universität Berlin / Grenoble INP_UGA G-SCOP laboratory / Université Grenoble Alpes / HSU – Helmut-Schmidt University / Université de Lorraine / Zentrum für Soziale Innovation GmbH / Inova+, Innovation Services, S.A / Maker V-10 / Stichting Dyne.Org / Bauhaus-Universität Weimar / Fab City Hamburg E.V. / Hiww Ug / SUPSI University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland / Mekanika / Metalab / TMDC

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